
Strategic Economic Audit of the West of England

An evidence-led assessment of the region's
strengths, challenges and opportunities

19 March 2026

Connect with us

Email

thebrunelcentre@bath.ac.uk

Website

www.thebrunelcentre.co.uk

Follow us on Bluesky

[@thebrunelcentre.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/thebrunelcentre.bsky.social)

Follow us on LinkedIn

[linkedin/company/thebrunelcentre](https://www.linkedin.com/company/thebrunelcentre)

The Brunel Centre

The Brunel Centre is a newly established university-business partnership led by the University of Bath, UWE Bristol and Futures West.

Officially launched in July 2025, the Centre is dedicated to supporting sustainable and inclusive economic growth across the West of England by providing publicly accessible, real-time economic intelligence.

Based in Bath and Bristol, it works closely with regional authorities, businesses and policymakers to co-develop strategies that drive productivity, investment, clean growth and high-quality local employment.

This Strategic Economic Audit of the West of England is the first major research publication from the Brunel Centre, providing an evidence-led analysis of the West of England economy.

Contents

Executive summary	7
Key findings	8
Conclusion	11
Introduction	13
Scope	14
The West of England	15
Productivity, R&D and innovation	17
Introduction	17
Productivity	18
R&D investment	21
Innovation activity	25
Innovation clusters	29
Higher education and public research organisations	31
Qualitative industry insights	35
Summary	37
Business, enterprise and trade	41
Introduction	41
Structural change	42
Sectoral composition	42
Firm dynamism	44
Barriers to growth and SME challenges	47
Trade and export	49
Foreign direct investment	50
Summary	53
Labour market	56
Introduction	56
Employment	56
Earnings	58
Qualifications and skills	60
Economic resilience and shocks	61
Workforce structure	63

Youth participation	64
Commuting patterns	65
Summary	65
Skills and education	68
Introduction	68
Educational attainment – a competitive advantage	69
STEM strength	70
Professional performance	70
A tale of two tiers	72
Job matching success	74
Home to work	75
Summary	75
Migration	78
Introduction	78
Mobility in the region	78
Migration trends	80
Migration and higher education	85
Household types and migration pathways	86
Summary	87
Infrastructure	89
Introduction	89
Digital	89
Housing	91
Transport	93
Integration	94
Summary	95
Environment	97
Introduction	97
Greenhouse gases	97
Natural environment	104
Land use, net zero and nature recovery	105
Climate adaptation	107
Summary	107
Inequalities	111
Introduction	111
Structural inequality	112

Food insecurity	114
Child opportunity, health and future economic capacity	116
Crime as an indicator and driver of structural inequality	120
Labour market participation and economic inclusion	122
Summary	123
Conclusion	126
References	130

Executive summary

A region with exceptional potential — held back by structural constraints

The West of England is one of the UK's strongest regional economies. It benefits from a highly-skilled population, internationally competitive universities, globally significant industrial clusters and strong export performance. Nearly half of residents hold a degree, well above the national average, giving the region one of the deepest talent pools in England. Bristol and Bath attract high volumes of young workers, graduates and international students, reinforcing a dynamic labour market and offering a strong pipeline of future skills.

Yet the region's ability to convert this strength into broad-based, long-term sustainable and inclusive growth is being constrained by underlying structural and investment challenges. Housing affordability pressures, congested and unreliable transport, uneven digital connectivity and gaps in higher-level skills provision outside its cities are limiting productivity, restricting labour mobility, reshaping population patterns and widening inequalities. Small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), especially outside high-growth tech and creative sectors, face a fragmented support ecosystem and barriers to scaling. Climate pressures, land-use constraints and declining natural assets further challenge the region's economic resilience.

The findings of this report need to be interpreted within the wider national context, where the UK as a whole has faced persistently weak economic performance and low productivity growth since the global financial crisis of 2007-09. While the West of England's annual growth rate has significantly exceeded the national average since 2008, its progress has inevitably been shaped by this broader period of subdued growth and uncertainty. This national backdrop helps to explain the caution reflected in business sentiment and underscores why regional strengths alone have not translated into the levels of productivity and investment needed for more inclusive and sustainable long-term growth.

Key findings

Overall economic performance

- The West of England is one of the UK's strongest regional economies, powered by highly-skilled labour, globally competitive universities and leading industrial clusters.
- In 2023, the West of England took the lead as the most productive combined authority area in England outside of London, surpassing Cambridge and Peterborough.
- Its gross value added (GVA) growth averaged 1.9% from 2008-23, outperforming England's 1.35%, underpinned by increases in information and communication, professional services and specialised advanced engineering. Since 2020, the region's recovery has been markedly stronger than the UK average.
- The region effectively adapted to Brexit, with exports rebounding fast – EU exports rose 19% above pre-pandemic levels by 2023 and non-EU exports surged 33% – reinforcing a shift towards global markets and reflecting the global orientation of the region's aerospace sector.
- It generated £9.5 billion in exports in 2022, maintaining a significant trade surplus in sharp contrast with the UK's £44.1 billion trade deficit.
- It has a consistent 5% wage premium over the UK (excluding London) with even higher premiums in the creative (7%), green (9%), digital (10%) and advanced manufacturing sectors (12%), reflecting its strong labour market and concentration of high-skilled jobs.
- The region has an educational advantage that has been growing from 2015 onwards, with markedly more residents who have at least an undergraduate degree or higher – 46.9% compared with 37.6% in the rest of England.
- The West of England exhibits strong performance on job matching, with workers far less likely to be underemployed than those elsewhere in England – 28.6% versus 35.3% – a pattern consistent over the past decade and widening after the pandemic.

Structural challenges slowing growth

- Housing affordability is one of the region's biggest challenges: the average household in Bristol spent 44.6% of their income on rent, among the highest outside London.
- Transport congestion in Bristol and Bath are among the worst in the UK, restricting labour mobility, reducing productivity and constraining growth.
- SMEs face a two-speed ecosystem: technology firms thrive, while non-tech SMEs encounter fragmented support, constrained finance and weaker scaling pathways.

Labour market pressures and inactivity

- Employment is high at 79.3% compared with 75.7% for England, but economic inactivity is still a challenge, particularly in Bristol where 35% of the inactive population cite long-term illness and a high number are forced out of work due to caring responsibilities.
- Real wage growth in the region has been flat since 2015, underscoring the need for productivity increases to drive genuine improvements in living standards.
- Youth disengagement is increasing. Bristol's NEET (not in education, employment or training) rate for 16-17-year-olds has doubled since 2019 to nearly 6%, now well above the England average of 3.4%.
- SMEs show weakened post-pandemic labour demand, with smaller firms experiencing falling turnover growth compared with strong performance among large firms.

Need for better pathways into employment

- Job matching is strong in Bristol (graduate underemployment is 13.4% versus 21.2% nationally). But South Gloucestershire and North Somerset show higher underemployment and weaker alignment between qualifications and jobs.
- Despite pockets of strength, problems persist, with around 20% of the regional workforce overqualified and 25% underqualified for

their roles, while apprenticeship completion rates sit below 50% (comparable to national levels).

- All areas of the West of England perform below the national average for disadvantaged pupils at GCSE and in parts of Bristol only 3.7% of Free School Meal-eligible young people go on to achieve a degree by age 22, compared with 15.9% nationally.
- Rising youth NEET rates, skills leakage and underemployment in suburban and coastal areas highlight the need for place-sensitive employment pathways, targeted employer engagement and post-16 support.

Inequalities undermining long-term resilience

- More than 51,000 children in the region are living in absolute low income and youth mental health pressures are severe, especially in North Somerset.
- Food insecurity is structurally concentrated, with food banks in Bristol and North Somerset experiencing the highest parcels-per-site pressure.
- Child poverty sharply diverges across the region, with 23% in Bristol living in relative low-income households.

Environment and infrastructure constraints

- Transport is the region's largest emitter, responsible for 53% of emissions, with road transport accounting for 32%. Vehicle electrification alone will not be sufficient to meet the region's 2030 net-zero target, a significant challenge for a region heavily dependent on cars.
- At least a 19-fold gap in retrofit delivery threatens delivery of the home-energy upgrade targets that are critical to reducing domestic emissions and achieving net zero.
- The five highest-emitting sectors – which account for 60% of commercial and industrial emissions in the region – make up only 1.8% of total employment, suggesting that decarbonising those sectors can be achieved with minimal impact on the labour market.

-
- The region’s natural environment, one of its core competitive assets, is deteriorating, with 118 of 138 designated conservation sites now classed as ‘unfavourable’ and ‘declining’.

Conclusion

The West of England has exceptional strengths – a highly-skilled workforce, globally competitive sectors, resilient export performance and strong job-matching – yet its future success is increasingly constrained by structural pressures. Housing costs, congested transport, uneven SME support and labour-market inactivity are now acting as real barriers to inclusive and sustainable growth. At the same time, widening inequalities, youth disengagement and environmental degradation are eroding the foundations of long-term resilience.

The path forward is clear: the region needs to work collaboratively across the public, private and voluntary sectors to focus on productivity-led growth, facilitate stronger pathways into employment, take region-wide action on housing, transport, skills and inequalities, and enact an accelerated transition towards net zero. By addressing these constraints head-on, the West of England can translate its strong economic fundamentals into a more inclusive, resilient and sustainable model of long-term growth for the region and the UK.

Introduction

Lucy Martin, Joseph Marriott

Introduction

This report provides an independent, evidence-led analysis of the West of England economy, to guide effective place-based policy and strengthen regional collaboration.

The West of England is one of the UK's strongest regional economies, characterised by exceptional talent, globally competitive research institutions, internationally significant industrial clusters and a resilient business base. Yet the region's ability to translate these advantages into broad-based, long-term, sustainable and inclusive growth is increasingly constrained by deep structural pressures. Housing affordability, congested and unreliable transport, uneven digital connectivity and persistent inequalities are reshaping the region's economic geography and limiting the extent to which its strengths benefit people and places across the region.

This Strategic Economic Audit provides an independent, evidence-led assessment of these dynamics. Bringing together comprehensive quantitative analysis, qualitative industry insight and comparative regional evidence, the audit sets out a clear, objective understanding of the West of England economy. It identifies where the region performs strongly, where structural challenges are intensifying, and where long-term risks and opportunities are emerging.

The analysis spans productivity, innovation, skills, labour markets, business and enterprise, migration, infrastructure, the environment and inequalities. Across these domains, a consistent story emerges: the region's economic fundamentals are powerful, but the systems that enable inclusive and sustainable growth – housing, transport, skills pipelines, SME scaling conditions and environmental resilience – are under significant strain. Addressing these constraints is now central to unlocking the region's full economic potential.

The purpose of this audit is therefore threefold:

1. To create a shared evidence base: providing a clear, robust and region-wide understanding of economic performance, structural pressures and place-based disparities.
2. To support effective strategy and investment decisions: highlighting where targeted action is most needed to unlock productivity, improve inclusion and strengthen the region's resilience and long-term sustainability.
3. To enable coordinated, long-term collaboration across local authorities, businesses, universities, government and the voluntary, community and social enterprise (VCSE) sector, recognising that no single organisation can address the region's systemic challenges alone.

Scope

This audit offers a comprehensive view of the West of England economy, drawing primarily on official data from the Office for National Statistics (ONS) and administrative datasets. It is supplemented by qualitative insights from industry, stakeholders and business support providers, enabling a richer understanding of the lived experience of firms in the region.

The analysis covers the four constituent local authorities: Bath and North East Somerset, Bristol, North Somerset and South Gloucestershire. While the West of England performs strongly on many national indicators, the report also highlights substantial internal differences between these localities that shape opportunities, outcomes and long-term resilience.

Across the report, sustainable and inclusive economic growth is defined as the generation of additional economic activity that improves people's ability to thrive, strengthens long-term resilience, and avoids harm to society and the environment. This definition aligns the audit with regional ambitions for productivity-led, place-sensitive and low-carbon growth.

The West of England

The West of England is home to over 1.2 million people who contribute to its diverse and dynamic economy, combining globally significant clusters in advanced manufacturing, aerospace, digital technologies, creative industries and life sciences with high-quality universities and distinctive cultural and natural assets. Productivity levels are among the highest of any combined authority outside London, supported by strong innovation ecosystems and deep pools of highly-skilled labour.

Yet these strengths coexist with increasingly pronounced structural constraints. Housing affordability and availability – particularly acute in Bristol and Bath – restrict labour mobility, increase hiring costs and place pressure on households. Transport congestion and patchy connectivity limit access to opportunity and undermine productivity. Digital exclusion persists despite strong overall coverage. The region's natural environment is under stress, and the transition to net zero requires accelerated action across transport, buildings and high-emitting sectors.

Inequalities within the region are significant and growing. Pockets of high deprivation, widening youth mental health pressures, economic inactivity linked to long-term sickness and uneven access to good-quality work all shape long-term economic resilience. Structural pressures on SMEs, including constrained finance, fragmented support and capacity challenges, further hinder inclusive growth and contribute to an increasingly two-speed ecosystem.

Taken together, these forces underscore the need for coordinated, place-sensitive, system-wide action. The West of England has exceptional economic potential, but realising it requires the foundations of inclusive, productive and sustainable growth to be strengthened. This audit provides the evidence base to support that ambition.

Productivity, R&D and innovation

Chris Dimos, Aida Garcia Lazaro, Kieron Owen

Productivity, R&D and innovation

The West of England's economy is powered by strong productivity performance and a rapidly evolving innovation ecosystem, underpinned by high-value research and development (R&D) activity, emerging technology innovation clusters and leading research institutions. A small number of highly dynamic clusters spanning advanced manufacturing, digital technologies, life sciences and emerging deep-tech sectors are driving growth, innovation intensity and significant public R&D investment across the region.

Introduction

This chapter examines the West of England's productivity performance, R&D activity, innovation-active firms and innovation types using microdata from the Office for National Statistics (ONS) and data published by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT). It assesses productivity trends and investigates how productivity varies across sectors and types of firms. It also analyses the R&D intensity of the region and explores the likelihood of regional firms to invest in certain types of R&D investments and receive public R&D funding. The scale and characteristics of innovation across businesses in the region are evaluated, while barriers to innovation are identified. The analysis places the West of England in the context of all combined authorities across England by comparing key statistics.

This chapter also maps the West of England's innovation clusters, including activities within industrial strategy sectors, emerging technologies, real-time industrial classification (RTIC) sectors, and Innovate UK-engaged firms to understand their economic contribution, innovation intensity and access to public funding. Complemented by qualitative insights from industry, it integrates quantitative and qualitative evidence to identify drivers of regional productivity and to support the development of targeted, place-based economic and innovation policy for the West of England.

Productivity

In 2023, the West of England took the lead as the most productive combined authority in England outside of London, surpassing Cambridgeshire and Peterborough. Similar to the rest of the UK, it still falls significantly behind the Greater London Authority. Small- and medium-enterprises (SMEs) and foreign firms drive productivity alongside sectors with high capital intensity (e.g. electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply) or specialised knowledge (e.g. information and communication).

The West of England consistently ranks among the top three performing combined authority regions in England between 2009 and 2023 (see Figure 1, which plots labour productivity measured as gross value added (GVA) per hour worked). After a slight dip between 2010 and 2013, productivity rises steadily from 2013, reaching above £43 of GVA per hour worked by 2016-17. After a modest softening around 2018-19, the region's productivity increases again, peaking at approximately £45.20 of GVA per hour worked in 2023 – the highest value ever recorded across all combined authorities. Cambridgeshire and Peterborough, which was the forerunner in earlier years, records the second-highest productivity level at £42.30 of GVA per hour worked.

Nevertheless, all combined authorities remain below the productivity level of the Greater London Authority, which in 2023 stood at approximately £53 of GVA per hour worked. Compared with combined authorities such as the Greater Manchester, West Midlands and South Yorkshire, the West of England shows not only higher levels but also a stronger post-2014 growth trajectory.

Figure 1: Labour productivity of West of England and other combined authorities (2023 prices)

Source: ONS subregional productivity data by combined authority. For the West of England, also ONS productivity data by local authority district were used.

A Productivity in the region varies considerably across different sectors (see Figure 2, which reports sectoral labour productivity indexed to manufacturing (manufacturing = 100)). Several service sectors exhibit substantially lower productivity than manufacturing, including human health and social work (28), other services (examples include animal care, housekeepers and related services etc.) (29), accommodation and food (33) and education (36). Agriculture (47), administrative support (53) and wholesale and retail (59) also remain well below the manufacturing benchmark.

middle tier includes real estate (68) and arts and recreation (80), while professional, scientific and technical services (97) and transportation and storage (98) are broadly comparable to manufacturing.

Figure 2: Labour productivity across the West of England sectors

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS Annual Business Survey (ABS) microdata.

Note: Manufacturing = 100

In contrast, capital-intensive and infrastructure-related sectors are markedly more productive. Mining and quarrying (118) and construction (122) exceed manufacturing moderately, while financial and insurance activities (143) and the information and communication sector (152) have substantially higher productivity. Water supply and waste services (223) more than double manufacturing productivity. Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply stands out as an extreme outlier (560), reflecting very high capital intensity and output per hour. Overall, productivity differences align closely with sectoral capital intensity and specialised knowledge.

Firm size and ownership status can affect productivity too (see Figure 3). Both micro firms (≈ 86) and large firms (≈ 90) both underperform relative to SMEs (100). These differences possibly reflect organisational inefficiencies relating to size.

Figure 3: Labour productivity in the West of England by firm size and firm ownership

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS ABS microdata.

Note: SMEs = 100

In terms of ownership, foreign-owned firms outperform their domestic equivalents (indexed to 100), with productivity approximately 10% higher (≈ 110). The productivity premium of foreign-owned firms suggests that there are potential productivity gains to be had from attracting inward foreign direct investment (FDI) to the region, particularly in high-value sectors.

R&D investment

The West of England exhibits substantial R&D intensity overall, i.e. the ratio of R&D expenditure to turnover, amounting to 3.5%, placing it in the upper-middle tier of all combined authorities. It outperforms several authorities,

including West Midlands (3.2%), South Yorkshire (3.2%), Liverpool City Region (2.5%) and Tees Valley (1.5%). But it remains below authorities such as Greater Manchester (3.7%), North East (4.1%), York and North Yorkshire (5.0%) and there is a significant gap to Cambridgeshire and Peterborough, the most R&D intensive authority at 6.2% (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: R&D intensity in the West of England and other combined authorities

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS Business enterprise research and development (BERD) microdata.

R&D intensity varies by sector, which means there are marked differences between the combined authorities depending on the sectors concentrated in each place. The West of England's R&D structure appears to be less concentrated in knowledge-intensive sectors than other combined authorities, but it is relatively stronger in certain locally oriented and infrastructure-related industries (see Figure 5).

In the West of England, professional, scientific and technical activities (13.2%) and arts, entertainment and recreation (11.6%) have the highest R&D intensity. The region also records relatively strong R&D intensity in real estate (6.5%), transportation and storage (6.4%), water and waste services (4.7%), and accommodation and food services (4.6%). By contrast, R&D intensity is comparatively low in human health and social work (1.2%),

wholesale and retail trade (0.4%) and in other service activities (0.3%). Manufacturing (2.1%) and information and communication (2.1%) also display moderate-to-low intensity.

Figure 5: R&D intensity across West of England sectors (2009-23)

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS BERD microdata.

Notes: The following sectors are not reported to abide by the statistical disclosure control (SDC) rules of the ONS: 1. Agriculture, forestry and fishing, 2. Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, 3. Mining and quarrying, and 4. Public administration and defence.

R&D in other combined authorities is more heavily concentrated in professional, scientific and technical activities (16.4%) and arts and recreation (10.2%), while finance (0.8%) shows low R&D intensity. Further, the West of England exhibits lower R&D intensity than other combined authorities in information and communication, and manufacturing and health, but higher levels in sectors such as accommodation, real estate, transportation, finance and water services.

There are also systematic differences in innovation behaviour by firm ownership and size, with some contrasts between the West of England and other combined authorities. These are highlighted in Table 1, which reports the estimated probabilities that a firm (i) conducts basic research, (ii) undertakes applied research, (iii) engages in experimental development, and (iv) receives public R&D funding, disaggregated by firm ownership and

size for firms located in the West of England and in other combined authorities.

Table 1: Propensity to conduct R&D and receive public R&D support in the West of England and other combined authorities (disaggregated by firm ownership and firm size)

Firm type	Probability of conducting basic research (percentage points)		Probability of conducting applied research (percentage points)		Probability of conducting experimental development (percentage points)		Probability of receiving R&D support (percentage points)	
	West of England	Other CAs	West of England	Other CAs	West of England	Other CAs	West of England	Other CAs
Domestic (vs foreign)	3.8**	2.5***	0.1	0.5***	2.7**	0.5***	3.6**	2.6***
SMEs (vs micro)	3.4**	5.7***	-0.8	1.3***	-0.4	1.7***	4.3***	7.3***
SMEs (vs large)	19.3***	5.6	6.6**	4.2***	17.0***	3.7***	19.7***	6.2

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS BERD microdata using econometric model.

Notes: ***, ** correspond to the 1% and 5% levels of significance respectively. The regression includes sector and year dummies. Cluster-robust standard errors were used.

Domestic firms are significantly more likely than their foreign equivalents to conduct basic research in both the West of England (3.8 percentage points, - pp) and in other combined authorities (2.5pp). In the West of England, domestic firms are also more likely to undertake experimental development (2.7pp) and receive R&D support (3.6pp), while the estimate on applied research is not statistically significant. In other combined authorities, domestic firms show smaller but significant increases across all these activities. SMEs in the West of England are more likely to conduct basic research (3.4pp) and receive R&D support (4.3pp) than micro firms, but they show no discernible advantage in applied research or experimental

development. This pattern is even stronger in other combined authorities. Strikingly, SMEs are also substantially more R&D-active than large firms in the West of England.

Innovation activity

The West of England is also a region that innovates. It sits in the upper-middle tier of all combined authorities, with an overall innovation rate of 50% (i.e. 50% of firms in the region reported to have innovated in the 2020-22 period) (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Innovation-active firms in the West of England and other combined authorities (2020-22)

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS UK Innovation Survey (UKIS) microdata.

Note: product innovations refer to the introduction of a new or significantly improved good or service); process innovations include the implementation of a new or significantly improved production or delivery method); business strategic innovations relate to the introduction of new or significantly changed business practices, organisational methods, or strategic approaches, including changes in management, marketing strategy, organisational structure, or external relations); and overall innovation.

This puts the West of England just below the leading regions of Cambridgeshire and Peterborough (57.4%) and the North East (54.4%), and roughly on par with Lancashire and South Yorkshire (see Figure 6). The West of England, however, lies clearly above the national average of 36% (Department for Business and Trade, 2024).

The West of England has strength in process (43.4%) and business strategic innovation (36.2%), broadly competing with the most innovative combined authorities in these areas. By contrast, levels of product innovation in the West of England are more modest (23.7%), below the levels observed in several northern and Midlands authorities. Overall, the region’s innovation profile appears process- and strategy-oriented rather than product-led, which is consistent with its strong productivity performance.

Figure 7: Innovation barriers in the West of England and other combined authorities

Source: Authors’ analysis of ONS UKIS microdata.

Note: UKIS asks firms to rate each specified barrier to innovating as ‘not important’ (1), ‘low’ (2), ‘medium’ (3), or ‘high’ (4).

Firms in the West of England, nevertheless, face substantial barriers to innovation, most notably around skills shortages. The reported difficulty of finding qualified personnel appears slightly more pronounced in the region than in other combined authorities (see Figure 7). Similarly, information

technology and market information gaps are of greater concern for businesses in the West of England than elsewhere.

Economic risks, high direct innovation costs and regulation also appear to be obstacles for firms in the region, and at comparable or marginally higher rates than in other combined authorities. While the cost of finance appears to be an innovation barrier in the West of England, firms in the region report being less concerned about its availability than their peers in other combined authorities.

Overall, differences between the West of England and elsewhere are modest, indicating a broadly similar barrier structure, though skills shortages appear particularly salient in the West of England.

Figure 8: Innovation barriers in the West of England for SMEs and large firms

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS UKIS microdata.

SMEs in the region appear to face more pronounced innovation barriers than large firms (see Figure 8). For SMEs, the most prominent reported constraint is the lack of qualified personnel (2.19), followed by cost of finance (2.09) and UK government regulations (2.09). Compared with large firms, SMEs report greater difficulties with respect to UK Government regulations (2.09 versus 1.83), accessing finance (1.92 versus 1.74), and cost of finance (2.09 versus 1.87).

Lack of information technology is the only area where large firms report higher concerns than SMEs (2.00 versus 1.88). Both firm types report similar levels of concern regarding lack of market information and direct innovation costs.

Overall, the pattern suggests that financial and regulatory barriers weigh more heavily on SMEs, while skill shortages remain a major challenge for both groups.

Barriers to innovation are not uniform across sectors (see Figure 9). Firms in the manufacturing sector report highly-rated obstacles, and at a much higher rate in the West of England (2.45) than in other combined authorities (2.15). Administrative and support services also report stronger barriers in the West of England (2.03 versus 1.77). In contrast, information and communication (1.94 versus 2.00), professional, scientific and technical activities (1.93 versus 2.00), construction (1.75 vs 1.81) and wholesale and retail trade (1.80 versus 1.87) show slightly higher barrier intensity in other combined authorities.

Figure 9: Innovation barriers across West of England sectors.

Source: Authors' analysis of ONS UKIS microdata. Notes: Other sectors are not reported to abide by the statistical disclosure control (SDC) rules of the ONS.

Innovation clusters

The West of England hosts some of the most dynamic innovation clusters in the country – these clusters are where businesses are co-located, belong to the same sector, and are R&D- and innovation-active. We assess the West of England's innovation clusters by exploring four complementary types:

- (i) Industrial strategy clusters, which map onto the government's industrial strategy sectors.
- (ii) Real-time industrial classification (RTIC) clusters, which are designed to identify emerging and evolving sectors more effectively than standard industrial classification (SIC) codes.
- (iii) Emerging clusters, which are selected RTIC clusters whose data accuracy has been scrutinised by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT).
- (iv) Innovate UK clusters, which correspond to broader non-sector-specific clusters based on all businesses in the region that have engaged with Innovate UK between 2015 and 2025.

Industrial strategy clusters reveal a regional economy anchored by large, high-turnover service firms, including professional and business services (4,322 businesses; £12.3 billion turnover; 42,100 employees) and digital and technologies (in Bristol and South Gloucestershire) (3,717 businesses; £9.5 billion turnover; 44,380 employees). The creative industries cluster is sizeable by business count (>2,000 firms) but generates comparatively lower turnover (£1.6 billion), while financial services deliver high turnover (£7.9 billion) with fewer firms.

Life sciences is the smallest industrial strategy cluster by business numbers (151) but is the most innovation-intensive. Within the sector, 87% of firms are innovation-active and 72% are engaged with UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) or Innovate UK. Life sciences also has the highest patenting rate (13%) and substantial funding relative to scale (around £18.3 million from Innovate UK; £4.2 million from other UKRI grants; and indicative R&D tax credits based on qualifying expenditure).

Advanced manufacturing and digital and technologies (in Bristol and South Gloucestershire) show strong innovation activity (30% and 24%) and evidence of within-cluster collaboration. The sector also attracts large

public funding and significant private R&D (via qualifying expenditure and indicative tax credits). Notably, the Bristol-based digital cluster attracts markedly more public R&D support and collaboration than its Bath-based counterpart, despite similar innovation-active rates.

RTIC clusters provide granular insight into emerging and evolving technologies not well captured by SIC codes. The West of England hosts a diversified ecosystem ranging from high-employment clusters in net zero (7,560 employees) and the digital creative industries (3,350 employees) to high-output clusters, such as energy management (£4.0 billion turnover) and FinTech (£1.8 billion turnover).

Several small but strategic deep-tech clusters (e.g. quantum economy, photonics, future telecoms supply chain) are based in the region, in greater concentration relative to nationally-identified clusters of the same sectors. Innovation rates are high in technology-intensive clusters (e.g. future telecoms, internet of things (IoT), FinTech, AgriTech), while patenting varies significantly by sector (higher in science/engineering clusters; lower in creative and service-heavy clusters).

Collaboration – measured by joint Innovate UK applications – appears concentrated in a subset of clusters (e.g. net zero, energy management/generation, quantum economy), consistent with shared infrastructure needs. Support via R&D tax credits goes hand in hand with UKRI funding in most cases, with the notable exceptions being cloud computing (less than £500,000 from UKRI and approximately £40 million in R&D tax credits), FinTech (around £1 million from UKRI and more than £100 million in R&D tax credits), and software as a service (just above £500,000 from UKRI and around £60 million in R&D tax credits).

The largest emerging cluster by scale is in the digital economy (4,385 sites; 33,220 employees; £6.9 billion turnover) but levels of innovation and patenting intensity are lower in this sector than other emerging technology areas, albeit with substantial R&D support because of its size. Several capital-intensive sectors deliver very high turnover from relatively few sites, including advanced materials (42 sites; £2.9 billion turnover) and semiconductors (49 sites; £3.4 billion turnover), while the space economy and materials innovation combine large employment figures with multi-billion-pound turnover.

Innovation performance is exceptionally strong across most emerging cluster sectors. Quantum technology, advanced connectivity,

semiconductors, materials innovation, artificial intelligence (AI) and the space economy all report innovation-active rates above 90%, high rates of engagement with Innovate UK/UKRI (exceeding 80%), strong patenting (quantum is $\geq 90\%$), and evidence of within-cluster collaboration. Engineering biology clusters show high innovation activity but limited observed collaboration, likely reflecting low grant volumes rather than an absence of networking.

Finally, a cross-sector Innovate UK cluster captures the West of England's most R&D- and innovation-intensive firms. This cluster is sizeable (2,395 sites; 112,770 employees; ~£32.4 billion turnover) and accounts for 4% of UK clustered locations (2% of all UK business locations). Nearly all firms are innovation-active and UKRI-engaged (both at 98%). Across all combined authorities, the West of England's Innovate UK cluster ranks as the third largest in terms of firm sites (Greater Manchester jointly with Liverpool City: 6,364; West Midlands: 2,752; West of England: 2,395), the fourth largest in employment (Greater Manchester jointly with Liverpool City: 296,840; West Midlands: 138,830; West Yorkshire: 133,290; West of England: 112,770), and the fifth largest in turnover (Greater Manchester jointly with Liverpool City: £92 billion; West Midlands: £88 billion; West Yorkshire: £76 billion; Hull and East Yorkshire: £42 billion; West of England: £32 billion).

The West of England Innovate UK cluster has a very high innovation rate (98%), similar to the rates of other combined authorities. However, its patenting rate (18%) is the lowest across all combined authority Innovate UK clusters (average of 24%). The region's consistently high innovation rates, both at the firm and cluster levels, suggest that the comparatively low patenting rate may not indicate weak innovation performance. Rather, it may reflect the fact that a substantial share of regional innovation – such as software development, process innovation and systems integration – is not patent intensive.

Higher education and public research organisations

The West of England is home to four universities, with two of them based in Bristol and/or South Gloucestershire (the University of Bristol and the University of the West of England) and two in Bath and North East Somerset (the University of Bath and Bath Spa University). All four institutions are

major regional employers and contribute substantially to R&D and innovation across a range of sectors. Collectively they attract research funding, drive high-impact academic work and support knowledge-intensive business activity in areas such as advanced engineering, digital technologies, creative industries, health sciences and sustainable technologies.

These universities are active partners in regional innovation ecosystems and business support. They participate in collaborative consortia that translate academic research into commercial application and spin-off companies. One such example is Forcetek, a spin-off from the University of Bath that develops advanced physics-based AI analytics to measure and interpret athlete performance directly from video footage. The universities also contribute to business incubators and innovation partnerships such as the SETsquared partnership (the University of Bath and the University of Bristol are among the founding university partners) and Future Space (University of the West of England). Further, they help attract investment and talent to the region.

University-industry and cross-institution initiatives also play a key role in regional strategy. A recent example is the establishment of the Brunel Centre, a new collaborative research and data hub created by the University of Bath, the University of the West of England and Futures West, with funding from Research England. The Centre provides independent, real-time, open-access economic data and analysis for the West of England economy, helping businesses, policymakers and investors make evidence-based decisions in areas such as productivity, skills, innovation, trade and investment. Its work supports regional economic planning and the delivery of industrial strategy by linking academic expertise with business insight, identifying growth opportunities, mapping skills and supply chains, and producing strategic research that underpins sustainable and inclusive economic growth across the region. For more information on regional university spin-offs, partnerships, research centres and institutes see (Dimos and Pearce, 2023).

Table 2: Student enrolment in universities in the West of England (2023-24 academic year)

Universities	Arts & humanities	Social sciences	Natural sciences	Engineering & technology	Total
Bath Spa University	3,520	15,000	450	5,615	24,585*
University of Bath	485	8,385	5,595	5,240	19,705
University of Bristol	4,670	12,000	10,860	4,610	32,140
University of the West of England	4,330	15,920	8,210	7,465	35,925
Total	13,005	51,305	25,115	22,930	112,355

Source: DSIT innovation cluster map data.

*Approximately 2,000 of all Bath Spa University students are based in its London campus.

Table 3: University income and expenditure in the West of England in £millions (2023-24 financial year)

Universities	Research income	Teaching income	Other income	Total income	Total expenditure	Income intensity	Expenditure intensity
Bath Spa University	10.1	176.6	16.6	203.3	192.8	8,269	7,842
University of Bath	91.8	219.5	79.9	391.2	316.0	19,852	16,036
University of Bristol	421.3	459.9	210.7	1,091	797.6	33,973	24,816
University of the West of England	44.7	287.8	71.0	403.5	396.0	11,231	11,023
Total	567.9	1,143	378.2	2,089	1,702	18,600	15,152

Source: DSIT innovation cluster map data.

The four universities collectively enrolled 112,355 students in the 2023-24 academic year (see Table 2). Social sciences are the largest subject area across all universities, accounting for 51,305 students, followed by natural sciences (25,115), and engineering and technology (22,930). The University of the West of England has the largest total student population (35,925), followed by the University of Bristol (32,140). Bath Spa University has a strong concentration in arts and humanities (3,520) and engineering and technology (5,615), but relatively small enrolments in natural sciences (450). The University of Bath shows a more balanced profile, with notable strengths in social sciences (8,385) and natural sciences (5,595).

From a financial perspective, the four universities generated £2.09 billion in total income in 2023-24, with their total expenditure amounting to £1.70 billion (Table 3). This highlights the pivotal role the higher education sector plays in the West of England, not only around knowledge creation, knowledge exchange and talent attraction but also in terms of economic impact. The University of Bristol is the largest institution financially, with £1.09 billion in total income, driven by substantial research (£421.3 million) and teaching income (£459.9 million). The University of Bath reports a strong research profile, generating £91.8 million in research income from a comparatively smaller student base. Indeed, the university's total income intensity (i.e. total income divided by the total number of students) amounts to approximately £20k per student, second only to the University of Bristol with approximately £34k per student. The University of the West of England and Bath Spa University exhibit lower income intensities with approximately £11k and £8k respectively. These two universities are more teaching-intensive and this is reflected in the higher concentration of their income that comes from teaching activities relative to research.

All four universities play an important role in developing the skills base of the region's innovation ecosystem. Each fulfils a distinct function within the ecosystem, providing complementarity rather than engaging in direct competition.

Overall, the universities within the West of England are key drivers of R&D and innovation in the region. They contribute significantly to its economic growth by creating and disseminating knowledge to regional industry and government, developing high-level skills, and supporting and incubating start-ups, scale-ups and R&D-led enterprises. By engaging in cutting-edge research, fostering industry partnerships, and providing innovation infrastructure and talent, the four universities help strengthen the region's

innovation ecosystem and enhance its competitiveness in knowledge-intensive sectors.

The West of England is also home to three Catapults both based in the Bristol area: NCC belonging to the High-Value Manufacturing Catapult network, the South West Digital Catapult, and the Compound Semiconductor Applications (CSA) Catapult (based in Newport but its future telecoms hub is in the Bristol and Bath Science Park). The NCC supports the development and industrialisation of advanced composite materials by bridging the gap between cutting-edge innovation and industrial application. It works with industry, academia and government to accelerate innovation, improve manufacturing capability and strengthen regional and national competitiveness in sectors such as aerospace, automotive, energy and construction. The South West Digital Catapult supports businesses, especially SMEs, to adopt advanced digital technologies. It does so by providing access to expertise, facilities and collaborative programmes in areas such as AI, immersive technologies and data-driven innovation, helping to drive not only regional digital transformation but also regional economic growth. The CSA Catapult accelerates the commercialisation of compound semiconductor technologies in the UK. It supports innovation through applied R&D, prototyping, testing facilities and industry collaboration. The Catapult works with businesses, universities and government to develop applications in areas such as power electronics, telecoms, photonics and advanced sensing.

Qualitative industry insights

This qualitative analysis complements the preceding quantitative evidence and aims to capture aspects that cannot be fully explored through survey-based (quantitative) data alone. Our analysis provides insights into West of England's industry perceptions of:

- i. their R&D and innovation activities, including how businesses define and identify themselves as R&D-active or innovative;
- ii. the role of R&D processes in generating productivity gains;
- iii. the role of financial constraints in R&D and innovation; and

-
- iv. the role of innovation, especially process innovation, in enhancing productivity.

To this end, we conducted semi-structured interviews with a range of private and public stakeholders, including representatives from the wider aerospace sector and from innovation accelerator organisations (funded through public or private sources). The analysis focuses on the aerospace sector for two main reasons. First, adopting a single-sector focus enables greater depth rather than breadth, allowing for a detailed exploration of productivity drivers and barriers within an innovation-intensive context. Second, aerospace represents a key driving force within the West of England economy, with a strong concentration of R&D activity, high-value manufacturing and established links between industry, academia and public institutions.

The perspectives and experiences of stakeholders and key informants involved in this aerospace case study offer a number of key findings. First, the terms R&D and innovation are often conflated in practice, creating some confusion about what they mean for businesses. Many participants used the two terms interchangeably, while others distinguished between them and recognised that innovation is often an outcome of R&D activity. This distinction is important because it shapes how firms conceptualise their activities, measure performance and engage with support mechanisms. A blurred understanding may lead businesses to underreport R&D, overlook eligible funding opportunities or misalign internal strategies with external policy frameworks.

Second, while some participants acknowledged that R&D can generate new products and open up market opportunities, they expressed doubts about how this can translate into significant productivity gains. This is important because it highlights a perceived disconnect between innovation activity and measurable economic performance. If firms do not associate R&D with improvements in efficiency, cost reduction or output per worker, they may prioritise short-term commercial outcomes over longer-term productivity-enhancing investments. Addressing this gap requires clearer evidence, better diffusion of best practice and support mechanisms that help firms to translate technological advances into operational and organisational improvements.

Third, participants expressed concern about the cost of R&D. They emphasised that the economic value of R&D depends not only on generating new ideas but on a firm's capacity to commercialise innovative

products at scale. This typically requires sustained, long-term investment and the ability to absorb upfront costs before returns materialise. Several participants highlighted the practical tension between investing in R&D and maintaining day-to-day operations, noting the need to balance research expenditure with production and sales activities that allow businesses to 'pay the bills' while continuing to innovate. This underscores the financial risk inherent in R&D-intensive strategies and the importance of stable cash flow, patient capital and R&D support mechanisms to sustain innovation over time.

Finally, some participants argued that while their product innovations enhance productivity for their customers, this in turn exposes their own need to improve internal productivity in order to remain competitive and sustain innovation. In their view, continued success depends less on further product development and more on strengthening in-house efficiency through process innovation, whether through improvements in production methods, workflow optimisation, digitalisation or organisational practices. This highlights an important dynamic: product innovation may generate external productivity gains, but long-term competitiveness often rests on a firm's capacity to innovate internally, reducing costs and improving operational performance alongside technological advancement.

Summary

The West of England is currently the most productive among all combined authorities, having consistently ranked within the top three over the period between 2009 and 2023. The region's R&D intensity stands at 3.5%, placing it in the upper-middle tier of the national distribution. While this reflects a relatively strong R&D profile compared with many northern and Midlands authorities, it remains below the regions with the very highest R&D intensity. A similar pattern emerges for innovation activity, where the West of England sits in the upper-middle tier overall but there are four authorities with stronger innovation uptake.

As a result, mitigating the reported barriers to innovation should be a central policy priority. In particular, skills shortages emerge as a particularly acute constraint and one that may be restrict the region's ability to sustain and scale its innovation performance. Addressing this challenge through targeted skills development, advanced technical training and stronger

industry-education linkages will be critical to unlocking further productivity and R&D and innovation growth.

SMEs are a key engine of growth in the West of England. They combine strong productivity performance with high levels of R&D intensity, playing a central role in the region's innovation ecosystem. Despite this dynamism, SMEs appear to face more pronounced innovation barriers than large firms, including financial constraints, market domination by established firms, UK government regulatory burdens and skills shortages. This tension highlights the importance of targeted policy support to sustain SME-led innovation and prevent structural barriers from constraining the region's growth potential.

Foreign-owned firms in the West of England exhibit a clear productivity premium relative to domestic firms, suggesting that inward FDI is associated with higher efficiency and performance. However, they are less likely to undertake R&D activities locally or to receive public R&D funding, implying that a significant share of their research activity may be conducted overseas. Despite this, foreign-owned firms remain important to the regional economy. Their high productivity contributes directly to aggregate performance, and they can play a valuable role in knowledge exchange, supply chain development and the diffusion of managerial and technological best practice. More effectively integrating foreign-owned firms within the local innovation ecosystem could therefore encourage R&D activity that takes place locally, enhance spillovers and deepen regional impact.

The West of England hosts a highly diversified cluster ecosystem that combines economic scale with technological depth. Large service clusters (particularly professional and business services and digital in Bristol) anchor employment and turnover, while smaller sectors (in terms of employment) such as life sciences and advanced manufacturing punch above their weight in terms of innovation intensity and research engagement. Emerging and RTIC clusters highlight clear strengths in deep-tech and capital-intensive areas – including quantum, semiconductors, advanced materials and space – many of which show high national concentration and strong UKRI engagement. The region's cross-sector Innovate UK cluster is one of the largest outside London, confirming its national innovation significance. Although patenting rates are relatively low, this likely reflects the prominence of non-patent-intensive innovation in the region, rather than necessarily weak performance.

The 'holy grail' of innovation policy is productivity growth. The West of England achieves the highest productivity among combined authorities, despite not ranking at the very top on conventional measures of R&D intensity or innovation uptake. But these indicators primarily capture the *quantity* of R&D and innovation rather than their *quality* or effectiveness. It is therefore plausible that the region's R&D and innovation activities are particularly high-value, enabling strong productivity performance even at mid-to-high levels of measured intensity.

This motivates an important agenda for future research: establishing how R&D investment translates into productivity in the West of England. In particular, what are the returns to R&D in terms of additional regional GVA? Do different types of R&D, including basic research, applied research or experimental development, have distinct impacts on productivity? And how do these relationships compare with those observed elsewhere in the UK? Answering these questions would help to clarify whether the region's productivity advantage reflects especially effective R&D and innovation, or if it lies elsewhere.

Business, enterprise and trade

Armagan Gezici, Paweł Capik, Kieron Owen

Business, enterprise and trade

The West of England is a high-performing, globally connected economy with standout strengths in advanced manufacturing, digital technologies and creative industries, but beneath the surface, growth is increasingly uneven and key structural pressures are intensifying. This chapter lifts the lid on the region's real trajectory, revealing a dynamic business base, world-class export engines and deep pools of talent. It also identifies risks – rising inequality, weakening HQ functions, small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) fragility and widening gaps between places – that must be addressed to ensure continued economic success.

Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the business base in the West of England, examining the structure, evolution and dynamics of the region's 49,000 enterprises. This analysis focuses specifically on business composition, trends and the challenges facing firms in the region within the national context while also highlighting important differences across its four constituent local authorities: Bath and North East Somerset, Bristol, North Somerset and South Gloucestershire.

Structural change

The West of England outperformed England overall with 1.9% average annual real gross value added (GVA) growth between 2008 and 2023 (versus 1.35% for England). At the individual sector level, manufacturing declined overall but specialised advanced engineering segments grew, reflecting structural evolution. Information and communication showed explosive growth (8.6% annually) and professional services expanded strongly, but head offices and management consultancy collapsed (likely due to headquarter relocations as a consequence of Brexit uncertainty in 2015-16 and restructuring due to the COVID-19 pandemic from 2020 onwards). Administrative and support services posted very high growth over the 2008-23 period, partly due to outsourcing trends. Post-pandemic recovery was exceptionally strong in the West of England, with the region diverging from national trends since 2020, through a significantly higher rate of growth than the UK average.

Sectoral composition

The sectoral structure of the West of England economy underpins its productive capacity, employment base and long-term growth prospects. The region's business base is unevenly distributed. Bristol hosts 20,190 enterprises (41% of the total), followed by South Gloucestershire (10,730, 22%), North Somerset (9,590, 19%), and Bath and North East Somerset (8,855, 18%). These patterns reflect distinct local specialisations – from Bristol's professional and financial services cluster to South Gloucestershire's aerospace corridor, Bath's heritage-tourism economy, and North Somerset's logistics networks.

The region has a distinctive service-led economic profile, with professional, scientific and technical activities representing the largest contributor to GVA. Administrative services are unusually strong compared with national averages, reflecting sizeable high-productivity operations. Although manufacturing accounts for a smaller share of employment, it remains a high-value sector dominated by aerospace and advanced engineering. Overall, the region's economic structure aligns closely with national industrial strategy sectors and is characterised by strong cross-sector interdependencies.

Productivity is highly uneven within the region and across sectors. South Gloucestershire far exceeds UK averages due to its aerospace and advanced

manufacturing industrial base, whilst Bristol, Bath and North East Somerset, and North Somerset sit below the England benchmark. Long-term productivity divergence is widening, with South Gloucestershire driving regional performance.

Table 4: Sectoral Distribution of Businesses, Employment and Output in the West of England

Sector	Share of GVA in the UK (%)	Share of GVA in the region (%)	Share of employment in the region (%)	Share of enterprises in the region (%)
Professional, scientific & technical activities	8.30	9.19 (1st)	11.05 (3rd)	17.26 (1st)
Administrative & support service activities	5.27	9.10 (2nd)	7.73 (7th)	8.55 (6th)
Manufacturing	9.13	8.78 (3rd)	5.52 (9th)	4.45 (9th)
Human health & social work	8.2	8.52 (4th)	13.70 (1st)	4.28 (10th)
Wholesale & retail trade; repair of vehicles	9.90	8.69 (5th)	12.22 (2nd)	12.34 (3rd)
Education	6.18	7.29 (6th)	8.84 (4th)	1.75 (15th)
Public administration & defence	5.05	6.50 (7th)	5.82 (10th)	0.26 (17th)
Construction	6.26	6.14 (8th)	5.30 (11th)	14.46 (2nd)
Information & communication	5.9	6.13 (9th)	5.89 (8th)	8.47 (7th)
Financial & insurance activities	8.79	5.77 (10th)	3.96 (13th)	2.60 (12th)
Real estate activities (excl. imputed rent)	3.56	3.33 (12th)	1.95 (15th)	4.10 (11th)
Accommodation & food service activities	2.82	2.30 (13th)	7.07 (6th)	6.44 (5th)
Arts, entertainment & recreation	1.38	1.01 (15th)	2.21 (14th)	2.73 (13th)

Source: ONS regional gross value added (balanced) by industry (local authorities); Business Register and Employment Survey (BRES); UK Business Counts (Inter-Departmental Business Register, via NOMIS).

Table 4 summarises how enterprises, jobs and GVA are distributed across major sectors in 2023, highlighting the sectors that most significantly contribute to regional output and how these compare with UK averages.

The professional, scientific, technical and information services sectors represent the region's largest enterprise base and its primary engine of growth. These are sectors dominated by a dense concentration of SMEs. Within established technology and creative clusters, firms benefit from rapid-access, high-trust networks that enable swift connections to advisers, investors and specialist service providers. While businesses operating outside these clusters often face more fragmented support and lower visibility of available services. While local universities provide strong research capability, SMEs frequently encounter structural barriers that make collaboration difficult. Despite these challenges, the creative and digital industries continue to show exceptional growth, supported by globally recognised institutions, such as the BBC Natural History Unit and Aardman.

Manufacturing in the region is high-value and capital-intensive, anchored by a globally significant aerospace cluster. Major firms such as Airbus, Rolls-Royce, GKN Aerospace and BAE Systems form the core of an integrated supply chain supported by numerous specialist SMEs. Alongside these established strengths, new areas of activity are emerging, including electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) aviation led by Vertical Aerospace, and a growing semiconductor and electronics ecosystem within the 'Silicon Gorge'. For early-stage companies, development models tend to be led by intellectual property (IP) rather than production, which contributes to ongoing challenges around retaining value locally as firms scale.

Firm dynamism

The region's economic vitality depends on continuous business turnover, supported by strong entrepreneurial ecosystems that combine assets like universities, skilled labour, finance and trust-based networks to encourage innovation and 'entrepreneurial recycling'. Such environments enable firms to form, grow and adapt, with churn acting as a mechanism for long-term competitiveness rather than instability. However, ecosystems differ in their ability to both generate new enterprises and to retain value as firms mature, with some regions losing economic gains through external acquisition. Understanding whether the West of England creates sustained local value or

mainly incubates firms that scale elsewhere requires an examination of both quantitative indicators of business dynamism and the qualitative factors that shape founders' decisions to grow locally or exit.

Business demography

Business dynamics indicate slow but steady growth: enterprise birth and death rates sit just below national averages, but net churn remains slightly positive, supported by a relatively strong share of high-growth firms – around 1,000 across the region, most of them in Bristol. Spatial differences are pronounced: Bristol leads on business formation and scale-ups, Bath and North East Somerset shows the strongest net churn, South Gloucestershire aligns with regional norms, and North Somerset experiences slight contraction (see Table 5).

Table 5: Business dynamism indicators by local authority, 2023 (including weighted regional average)

Local authority	Business stock	High-growth (%)	Birth rate (%)	Death rate (%)	Net churn (%)	Micro (%)	Small (%)	Medium (%)	Large (%)
Bath and North East Somerset	8855	5.10	9.66	8.64	+1.02	88.24	9.85	1.43	0.48
Bristol	20190	6.10	11.19	10.70	+0.50	86.52	10.98	1.96	0.54
North Somerset	9590	4.90	10.79	11.00	-0.21	89.71	8.74	1.22	0.33
South Gloucestershire	10 730	5.40	10.62	10.21	+0.42	88.95	9.18	1.53	0.35
West of England (weighted average)	49365	5.54	10.71	10.28	+0.44	87.98	9.95	1.63	0.45

Source: ONS (2025) Business Demography and UK Business datasets; author's calculations.

Note: 'Net churn' = $100 \times (\text{births} - \text{deaths}) \div \text{active enterprise stock}$, using enterprise counts rather than rate differences. Regional values are derived from aggregated births, deaths and stocks across local authorities, consistent with ONS (2025) and OECD (2023) methods.

The pattern of firm size broadly mirrors the national picture, being dominated by micro-enterprises, though Bristol and South Gloucestershire host a thicker layer of medium-sized firms linked to knowledge-intensive sectors and advanced manufacturing.

Trends from 2018-23 show a resilient but mature ecosystem: strong pre-pandemic churn, a compression of births and deaths during COVID-19, and a stabilisation to modestly positive churn by 2023. Across local authorities, the overall pattern is one of steady stability rather than rapid renewal, with Bristol consistently the most stable and Bath and North East Somerset showing the greatest year-to-year variability due to its smaller business base.

Interpreting formation and exit

Business formation in the region is shaped by diverse motivations, with a growing share of new enterprises emerging from economic necessity in a competitive labour market rather than entrepreneurial ambition. Many individuals leaving well-paid corporate roles start consultancies or small service businesses with the aim of replacing previous incomes rather than scaling significantly. This highlights the diversity in the region's micro-enterprise population, which includes both high-potential early-stage firms and stable, low-growth businesses whose limited scaling ambition reflects personal circumstances rather than market failure. Understanding this diversity is essential when interpreting growth barriers and designing support interventions.

Business insight

In qualitative interviews, a business-support provider noted that much of their work involves helping necessity-driven businesses emerging from shifting labour markets.:

“People are being made redundant... people coming out of larger businesses, corporate businesses have great skills but have never run a business before. Then want to offer their skills to the open market, we're getting a lot of that.”

A second key dimension concerns how value is retained, or lost, as firms exit. Bristol's successful high-growth businesses overwhelmingly leave through acquisition, often by overseas buyers, rather than public listings or local succession. Unlike ecosystems in Cambridge, Edinburgh or Manchester where patient capital, institutional coordination and strong investor

networks support initial public offerings (IPOs), local headquarters retention or entrepreneurial recycling, the West of England appears to have a more acquisition-oriented development pathway (Beauhurst, 2023); (Cambridge Enterprise, 2025) (ScaleUp Institute, 2023); (Scottish Financial News, 2026). This trend is reinforced by local support practices that actively encourage founders to plan for exit. While such exits reflect success for individual entrepreneurs, they risk creating an 'incubator economy' in which early-stage growth occurs locally but ownership, profits and strategic control migrate elsewhere, limiting long-term regional value capture.

Business insight

An interviewee in an organisation providing support for early-stage deep tech firms described their approach that is indicative of the 'incubator economy' theme that appeared across the dataset:

"[founders are] encouraged to think about how do they, what level do they take their company to before they sell it on? Because they're unlikely to be making the final product. They'll be selling on the [intellectual property] IP or the proven sort of commerciality of it. And they may stay and be part of the company and stuff. I'm not saying they're not, but they may leave and then it's made and sold by somebody else."

Barriers to growth and SME challenges

The West of England business ecosystem, like that of the rest of the UK, has suffered from a backdrop of muted economic performance that has led to lowering levels of investment and job creation, as well as increased levels of caution in the business community. The region's Chamber of Commerce Quarterly Economic Survey data reveal that most firms have seen flat sales for two years, with 55-65% reporting no change quarter-to-quarter and only 20-35% reporting increases. Investment intentions follow the same pattern: around half of businesses expect no change, while the share anticipating cuts rose to one-third by mid-2025. Rather than major contraction, SMEs are operating in a holding pattern, deferring decisions to expand, hire or invest.

Three barriers dominate. First, macroeconomic uncertainty overshadows everything else: over 80% of firms cite general economic conditions as a growing concern, and around 70% mention business uncertainty, far ahead of specific pressures like taxation or inflation. Second, access to finance has tightened. Qualitative evidence from business support professionals suggests that investment networks in the region concentrate around software and digitally scalable firms, reflecting the distinct financing structures of different sectors. However, the forms of finance that manufacturing and foundational-economy SMEs typically rely on have also become more constrained. Indeed, data shows that while gross bank lending to SMEs rose overall, the amount going to manufacturing declined (UK Finance, 2025). What's more, the British Business Bank identifies "significant finance gaps" in capital-intensive industrial strategy sectors where neither standard equity nor conventional bank debt adequately supports scale-up (British Business Bank, 2025). Third, workforce barriers operate at critical transition points. Making a first hire is perceived as "a minefield," deterring sole traders from growing. At the next stage, many SMEs hit management-capacity limits that stall expansion, requiring intensive board-level support to change systems or decision-making processes.

Business insight

During discussions on the West of England's business landscape, an interviewee in business financial support explained how the 'two-speed ecosystem' appears for non-tech businesses:

"the technology and digital and probably creative industries you'd put into that as well, the startup and the scale up sort of ecosystem... I would argue it's pretty well fully formed... If I was to map that across to a sector agnostic sort of startup or scale up style comparison, I don't think it would be the same... that ecosystem effect is sort of like fragmented and you get pockets of expertise."

SMEs outside high-growth clusters face additional structural disadvantages. A 'two-speed ecosystem' persists: firms in technology and creative industries benefit from embedded networks, rapid access to investors and advisers, and dense professional-services support, while firms in other

sectors encounter fragmented provision and rely on heavy signposting from intermediaries simply to identify available support. Meanwhile, small firms struggle with administrative burdens, lacking capacity to handle human resources (HR), finance and compliance without external help. Yet when support is well-targeted – for example through digitalisation programmes like Made Smarter – demand is strong, with take-up exceeding targets and waiting lists forming.

Crucially, our findings indicate that not all SMEs aspire to scale. Many were founded from economic necessity, with the goal of replacing previous incomes rather than pursuing growth. These firms contribute significantly to local economies even without scaling, particularly through employment, local spending and supply-chain activity.

Overall, the region's constraints stem less from lack of entrepreneurial activity and more from a combination of systemic uncertainty, fragmented support for non-tech sectors, limited finance options, and structural workforce barriers. Growth potential exists, but it is unevenly distributed – enabled for some, impeded for others – within an ecosystem that is stable but struggling to regain pre-pandemic momentum.

Trade and export

The West of England stands out nationally for maintaining a consistent trade surplus, driven by a powerful dual export engine, consisting of aerospace-led goods and high-value financial and professional services.

In 2022, the region generated £9.5 billion in exports, far exceeding its import bill and contrasting sharply with the UK's £44.1 billion national trade deficit (Office for National Statistics, ONS, 2023a). Exports have become a larger share of the regional economy, rising from 21.6% of GVA in 2021 to 28.4% in 2023, while imports stabilised at around 16-17% of GVA. Both goods and services contributed to the surge: goods exports rose from 9.3% to 13.2% of GVA, while services increased from 12.2% to 15.2%, with services now generating most of the export value.

The South West (Cornwall, Devon, Dorset, Bristol, Gloucestershire, Somerset and Wiltshire) adjusted well to leaving the European Union (EU) and entered the post-Brexit transition era with lower dependence on EU trade than the UK overall – 41% of the region's exports went to the EU in 2016, versus about 44% nationally – due to aerospace's global orientation.

Exports to the EU exports fell sharply in 2020 (-24%) but rebounded strongly to £18.3 billion by 2023, 19% above pre-pandemic levels, outperforming UK-wide recovery. Non-EU exports have grown even faster, rising 33% between 2019 and 2023 to reach £30.1 billion, shifting the region further toward global markets. But despite these strong aggregate numbers, small exporters have faced significant pressures: national studies show that 14% of UK firms stopped exporting to the EU after the Trade and Cooperation Agreement (TCA), with the smallest firms seeing a 30% drop in EU export volumes. This echoes the challenges identified in the SME evidence earlier in the chapter (ONS 2023a).

Trade performance is both enabled and constrained by regional infrastructure. Bristol Port handles 8-9 million tonnes of cargo per year and 550,000 vehicles, though rail gauge limits restrict competitiveness for container freight (Western Gateway STB, 2024). Bristol Airport reached 10 million passengers in 2024, with key business routes to Amsterdam, Paris, Frankfurt and Dublin; planned expansion to 12 million passengers will strengthen connectivity (Bristol Airport, 2024). Digital infrastructure remains uneven, with 16,000 households still lacking superfast broadband, despite national gigabit coverage reaching 84% (WECA, 2025a). Given that 68% of UK services exports are delivered remotely, universal digital coverage is now a core economic requirement (ONS, 2023b).

Overall, the region's export base is a genuine strategic strength—diverse, resilient, and growing faster than national patterns—but its long-term sustainability hinges on resolving infrastructure bottlenecks and ensuring growing firms can scale locally rather than being acquired and offshored. The trade surplus reflects real competitiveness; capturing more of this value domestically will depend on the region's ability to retain ownership and strategic control as export-oriented firms grow.

Foreign direct investment

Foreign direct investment (FDI)¹ remains an important source of capital, jobs, and global value-chain integration (the linking of all business processes from raw materials to end product) for the West of England. But recent

¹ Foreign direct investment (FDI) is cross-border investment made with the objective of establishing a lasting interest in the host economy. FDI is also defined by control relationships, where the direct investor (parent company) controls at least 10% of the voting power (ordinary shares) of the direct investment enterprise (ONS, 2025).

trends reveal sharp volatility and clear divergence from both UK-wide and global patterns.

Figure 10: FDI inflow dynamics 2017-23, % of previous year

Source: Authors' calculations based on ONS (2025), UN Trade and Development, UNCTAD (2022, 2025). Global flows measured in USD, UK and the West of England in GBP.

After several years of decline linked to Brexit uncertainty and the COVID-19 pandemic, the region experienced a dramatic surge in 2021: FDI inflows hit £3.7 billion, a 372% year-on-year increase, compared with 193% globally and 112% for the UK (see Figure 10). This record year coincided with the global post-pandemic rebound and a record 42 international projects secured by Invest Bristol & Bath (IBB). But flows dropped sharply thereafter – by 2023, the region recorded a net disinvestment of £78 million, even as global and UK inflows continued to rise.

FDI origins in the region (excluding North Somerset due to data availability) have shifted, but the United States (US) and EU remain the dominant sources, although with significant year-to-year volatility (see Table 6). The EU contributed £688 million in 2019, before falling to a net outflow of £213 million in 2023. US investment, however, has been steadier, contributing £273 million in 2023.

Table 6: FDI inflows to West of England (£ millions; excluding North Somerset)

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Africa, Australasia and Rest of World	c	c	c	7	-24	c	c	-51	5
Asia	c	c	-3	34	31	-7	11	-3	-43
<i>including Japan</i>	4	15	3	-1	10	7	9	1	low
Central and South Americas	7	20	c	75	-11	-4	-122	-42	-10
EU Europe	-1,571	586	282	26	688	c	203	392	-213
<i>Including:</i>									
<i>France</i>	-212	340	-15	37	c	13	c	c	-135
<i>Germany</i>	-463	267	184	172	34	-14	-47	24	5
<i>Luxembourg</i>	7	-57	17	-172	43	-39	4	-18	-16
<i>Netherlands</i>	c	12	63	-31	82	c	c	-26	-157
Non-EU Europe	2	c	-29	285	16	361	c	-75	-90
<i>including Switzerland</i>	-6	7	14	c	-45	c	c	6	42
North Americas	7	568	127	286	69	223	179	193	273
<i>including USA (incl. Puerto Rico)</i>	19	509	123	273	8	147	127	162	220
World total (i.e. FDI inflows to West of England)	-1,429	2,149	198	714	768	999	3,718	413	-78

Source: ONS data on foreign direct investment involving UK companies by UK country and region, (directional): inward (2025)

Note: "c" denotes values which have been suppressed to mitigate disclosure (by ONS) "low" denotes zero or value below £0.5 million. A negative sign (-) before values indicates a net disinvestment.

At a sector level, the picture has changed markedly: manufacturing FDI has declined over the decade; financial and insurance services have swung from strong inflows to a net outflow of -£416 million in 2023; while professional and support services consistently dominate, attracting over £1.1 billion in 2016 and remaining the strongest performer in 2023 (£203 million). Together, service sectors now account for over two-thirds of the region's total FDI stock.

Despite this turbulence, the region continues to attract strategic investments, in part due to Bristol's reputation as a vibrant, liberal highly-skilled city with a strong innovation brand. Investors emphasise access to skilled labour, R&D incentives and the existing business base, while qualitative evidence highlights the appeal of Bristol's "energy" and positive investor experience.

Good local authority engagement also matters to investors: supportive planning and streamlined decision-making are reported as differentiating factors in securing investment. However, early indications suggest that the region's strategic growth sectors (clean energy, digital, creative, advanced manufacturing) attract only modest FDI overall, though IBB continues to land projects in these priority areas.

Summary

The West of England has one of the UK's most dynamic business ecosystems, built on world-class strengths in advanced manufacturing, digital technologies and creative industries. Bristol anchors a dense network of high-growth firms and specialist services, while South Gloucestershire's aerospace cluster – home to global leaders like Airbus and Rolls-Royce – continues to drive productivity far above the national average. Yet these strengths mask growing structural vulnerabilities, including weakening headquarters functions, uneven business formation across places and persistent barriers that limit SME competitiveness and long-term value retention.

Across the region's 49,000 enterprises, business demography signals slow but steady growth. Enterprise birth and death rates sit just below the national average but remain positive overall, generating roughly 1,000 high-growth firms – with Bristol accounting for three-fifths of them. Yet the region operates a clear 'two-speed ecosystem': firms in digital, tech and creative clusters enjoy rapid access to investors, advisers and specialist services, while those in foundational and non-tech sectors navigate fragmented, hard-to-access support. Structural barriers – particularly finance constraints, management capacity gaps and workforce challenges – mean that many SMEs remain in a cautious, low-investment holding pattern.

Firm formation shaped by redundancy-driven self-employment creates many micro-businesses without scale-up ambitions. Meanwhile, high-growth

firms tend to exit the region through acquisition by external, often international, buyers. This creates an 'incubator economy risk': the West of England excels at generating early-stage innovation, but ownership, profits and strategic control frequently leak out of the region at the point of maturity. This stands in contrast to models in Cambridge, Edinburgh and Manchester, where stronger patient-capital networks support IPOs, local headquarters retention and deeper entrepreneurial recycling.

Despite these structural challenges, the region's global orientation remains a major asset. The West of England consistently delivers a large trade surplus, fuelled by aerospace exports and high-value financial and professional services. Exports reached £9.5 billion, rising to 28.4% of regional GVA, while imports stabilised around 16-17%. Both EU and non-EU markets have grown since the pandemic, with non-EU exports up 33% since 2019. But smaller exporters face persistent post-Brexit frictions and digital exclusion remains a barrier for service-led exporting.

Foreign direct investment brings additional volatility. After a record £3.7 billion inflow in 2021, the region saw a net disinvestment of £78 million by 2023, despite continued UK-wide growth. The US remains the most stable investor, but EU inflows have become highly erratic. Critically, FDI into manufacturing and financial services has weakened, while professional and support services continue to attract the bulk of investment. Investors emphasise Bristol's skilled workforce, innovation brand and 'energy', while also citing planning support and streamlined processes as competitive regional advantages.

Overall, the business ecosystem is resilient but uneven, capable of generating innovation at scale, yet constrained in retaining value, supporting SMEs and ensuring growth across all sectors and places. The region's long-term competitiveness now depends on reducing ecosystem fragmentation, strengthening value capture and modernising the support structures around trade, productivity and investment.

Labour market

Damian Whittard, Daniel Jin, Van Phan, Gustavo Guntren

Labour market

The West of England's labour market is strong, highly skilled and consistently outperforms national benchmarks, with higher-than-average employment, earnings and qualification levels. Yet beneath these headline strengths, the picture is uneven: outcomes vary markedly across local areas; following the pandemic, economic inactivity rose due to long-term sickness; new pressures are emerging from pockets of increasing youth disengagement; and smaller firms have been hit hardest by the pandemic's legacy.

Introduction

This chapter provides a broad overview of the West of England labour market, examining how the region performs across a wide range of headline indicators. Drawing primarily on official data from the Office for National Statistics (ONS) and related administrative sources, the analysis situates the West of England within the national context, while also highlighting important differences across its four constituent local authorities: Bath and North East Somerset, Bristol, North Somerset and South Gloucestershire.

Employment

The West of England's labour-market performance is strong, with an employment rate of 79.3% in 2025, and particularly high levels in South

Gloucestershire at 82.3%. This is above the average for England as a whole, at 75.7%.

Unemployment remains relatively low at around 4%, with the major change over the last decade being in Bristol's unemployment rate. This fell from around 8% in 2015 to about 4% by 2023-24, before rising to just under 5% most recently. Bath and North East Somerset, North Somerset, and South Gloucestershire generally sit between 2-5%, typically below Bristol.

Overall unemployment has declined across the region over time, with slight recent increases. Bristol's higher rates, especially in certain neighbourhoods, contrast with the near-full-employment conditions in South Gloucestershire, highlighting the need for place-based interventions to support more inclusive growth.

Economic inactivity in the West of England region is lower than nationally at 17.5% (national average is 21.2%), but rising levels of long-term sickness have become an increasingly significant driver both in the region and nationally (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Breakdown of economically inactive population

Source: ONS Annual Population Survey (03/2024-03/2025).

Among the economically inactive population in the West of England, students and people with long-term sickness are the most significant groups, both representing 29% of the inactive population, respectively higher than the English average of 27%.

The proportion of students in the economically inactive population is highest in Bath and North East Somerset (41%), which may in some part reflect the sociodemographic profile of the students. Bristol is the local authority with the highest proportion of individuals who are long-term sick in the region (35%), which will be affected by localised pockets of deprivation. The proportion who are inactive because they are looking after family is also high in this area (25%), and for some, their inactivity will be linked to the issue of caring for those with long-term sickness. This suggests that targeted localised investments aimed at improving health of the long-term sick could be particularly advantageous in Bristol.

Earnings

Workers in the West of England also earn slightly above the England average – median weekly pay in the region £783, compared with £770 nationally. Indeed, the region has maintained a consistent wage premium of around 5% relative to the UK excluding London², reflecting its strong labour market and concentration of high-skilled jobs.

This premium is particularly evident in occupations aligned with local and national industrial strategy priorities, where earnings tend to exceed national norms.

- Across all priority sectors, workers in the West of England earn statistically significantly higher hourly wages than national counterparts in both restricted and unrestricted models³.

² This analysis used de-identified individual-level data from the ONS Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings (ASHE) to provide an in-depth understanding of wage patterns across Great Britain. It uses regression analysis to examine whether there is a wage premium or penalty associated with working in the West of England and its four constituent local authorities.

³ The restricted model controlled only for individual and firm level characteristics, whilst the unrestricted model further controlled for both occupation and region.

-
- Advanced manufacturing and engineering: Large wage premium of ~15% (restricted) and ~12% (unrestricted), indicating strong sectoral pay performance.
 - Everyday economy: Smaller but positive premium of ~5% in the unrestricted model, showing that West of England wages exceed national averages even in lower-wage service sectors.
 - Creative industries: Persistent premium of ~7%, reflecting strong regional clustering in Bristol and Bath.
 - Digital technologies: Substantial premium of around 10% (unrestricted), linked to the region's strong digital ecosystem and tight market for high-skilled tech roles.
 - Environmental goods and services: Positive premium of ~9% (unrestricted), likely driven by rising demand for green skills and expanding sustainability roles.

The West of England consistently outperforms the UK (excluding London) across each of these five strategic sectors on real hourly wages, underpinned by knowledge-intensive industries, strong firm-level productivity and a highly-skilled workforce.

Our analysis also shows that wage premiums in priority sectors vary significantly across local authorities, reflecting their differing industrial strengths.

- Bath and North East Somerset performs well in the everyday economy (2%) and environmental goods and services (13%).
- North Somerset shows a notable premium in advanced manufacturing and engineering (18%).
- Bristol has broad-based wage advantages, particularly in digital technologies (10%), creative industries (8%), environmental goods and services (8%) and the everyday economy (7%), aligning with its role as the region's creative and digital hub.
- South Gloucestershire stands out for strong performance in advanced manufacturing and engineering (18%) and digital technologies (14%), consistent with its concentration of engineering, aerospace and high-tech employers.

Overall, our findings highlight a geographically varied pattern of wage strengths, suggesting that sector-focused economic policy should be tailored to the distinct industrial profiles of each local authority.

These observed advantages likely reflect a combination of agglomeration economies, human-capital concentration and sectoral specialisation. The region provides dense, diverse labour markets that encourage knowledge spillovers, collaboration and innovation. The persistence of a wage premium after adjusting for observable characteristics implies that unobserved factors – such as firm-level capital intensity, management quality, R&D activity and supply-chain integration – may play an equally important role in shaping local wage structures.

However, despite notable nominal pay advantages across the region, real wage growth has remained broadly flat since 2015, which is largely in line with national trends and means that rising earnings have not translated into meaningful improvements in purchasing power once inflation is considered. This pattern points to a labour market where real wages have struggled to gain momentum over time, underlining the importance of productivity-led growth strategies if the region is to achieve sustained and inclusive improvements in living standards.

Qualifications and skills

The West of England boasts a highly-qualified workforce, with 58.5% educated to Regulated Qualification Level 4 (RQF4) – equivalent to the first year of an undergraduate degree – or above. This is far above the England average and driven especially by Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset. Yet the region faces persistent skills mismatches, with around 20% of workers overqualified and 25% underqualified for their roles, and apprenticeship completion rates stuck below 50% across most areas (equivalent to the national average).

North Somerset and South Gloucestershire lag behind on higher-level qualifications, contributing to weaker skills use. At the same time, employers report shortages in specialist talent, exacerbated by an ageing workforce and reliance on London recruitment for niche roles. Qualitative evidence highlights bottlenecks in technical skills that take years to rebuild, and rising not in education, employment or training (NEET) rates, particularly in Bristol, signal growing gaps in post-16 engagement. Overall, strong qualification

levels are offset by structural weaknesses in skills pipelines, uneven use and demographic pressures, underscoring the need for targeted apprenticeship reform, better alignment with sector needs, and improved deployment of existing skills. For further in-depth analysis see the skills and education chapter of this audit.

Economic resilience and shocks

The West of England labour market has been relatively resilient to major shocks, such as COVID-19 and Brexit, but these have still had lasting impacts. Employment would have been higher in the absence of the pandemic, recovery has been uneven across local authorities, and Brexit has contributed to ongoing weakness in employment and higher inactivity.

A clear structural vulnerability emerging after the COVID-19 pandemic is the weakening growth performance of SMEs in the region. Before the pandemic, firms with 250-499 employees recorded the fastest employment growth, while those with over 500 employees saw the strongest turnover growth. These larger firms continued to perform well after the pandemic, while turnover growth declined sharply among firms with fewer than 100 employees (see Figure 12).

Overall, the evidence shows a widening gap in post-COVID growth between large companies and smaller firms, highlighting the disproportionate impact that the pandemic had on SME labour demand and business resilience in the region. Further investigation would be required to understand if this is a region-specific or national-level issue.

Figure 12: Growth by employment size band in West of England

(a) Year 2015-19

(b) Year 2020-24

Source: FAME database, Business Register and Employment Survey (BRES) data 2015-24.

Workforce structure

The West of England's workforce is shaped by a strong concentration of high-skilled employment, particularly in public administration, education and health, and in banking, finance and insurance, both of which exceed national averages. North Somerset and South Gloucestershire have more employment in manufacturing (including aerospace) and construction, reflecting distinct local specialisations (see Figure 13).

West of England workforce is largely dominated by professional occupations (35.3%), and to a greater extent than England as a whole which compares favourably to the England average (26.9%). Sub-regionally 55.7% of occupations in Bristol are either professional or associate professional, this is the highest of all West of England local authorities.

Figure 13: Employment by sector by local authority

Source: ONS Annual Population Survey (March 2025).

Working patterns remain relatively stable across the region, with full-time work predominating. Bath and North East Somerset stands out, having a

higher share of those in part-time roles, at 35% compared with 23% in England and 27% in the region overall.

One area of concern is the increasingly uneven access to good-quality work across the region. The Good Work Time Series – developed by the Institute for the Future of Work – assesses access to quality work across Great Britain by combining six dimensions: employment, economic activity, professional job share, de-routinisation, working hours and pay, into a single standardised score (Institute for the Future of Work, 2025). Between 2012 and 2024, the West of England’s four local authorities experienced a widening divergence. South Gloucestershire remained a strong performer throughout but was overtaken by Bristol in 2024. Bath and North East Somerset fluctuated but consistently sat in the lower half of regional performance, and North Somerset, despite early gains, fell to the lowest position by 2024.

Overall, the workforce structure reveals a resilient but uneven labour market, underpinned by strong sectoral and skills advantages but characterised by local differences in job quality, occupational mix and working patterns. This highlights the importance of tailored, place-based approaches to supporting progression and inclusive access to good work.

Youth participation

Youth participation across the West of England is increasingly uneven, with significant divergence emerging between local authorities. Overall, youth NEET rates (16-17-year-olds not in education, employment or training) remain relatively low in the region, but Bristol has experienced a marked and sustained rise from around 2.8% in 2019 to nearly 6% by 2025. The NEET rates in the city now exceed the England average (3.4%), signalling growing challenges in post-16 engagement.

In contrast, Bath and North East Somerset, South Gloucestershire and North Somerset have maintained low, stable NEET rates throughout the period, consistently outperforming national trends. The widening gap likely reflects underlying structural issues, including localised deprivation, differences in skills pipelines and variation in labour market opportunities.

The acceleration of NEET levels in Bristol stands out as a regional exception, widening the gap between the city and the other West of England authorities. The narrative emerging from the data is therefore one of increasing internal divergence within the region, with Bristol facing growing

challenges while its neighbours maintain relatively strong post-16 engagement.

Commuting patterns

Commuting patterns show that the West of England operates as a highly integrated labour market centred around Bristol, which attracts the largest volumes of daily commuters from South Gloucestershire and North Somerset. These strong cross-boundary flows highlight deep economic interdependence between the urban core and surrounding areas.

While commuting declined sharply during the COVID-19 pandemic – driven by the rapid rise of home and hybrid working – flows have partially recovered, though not to pre-pandemic levels. Hybrid working has now become a structural feature of the labour market, reducing long-distance commuting and placing greater importance on digital connectivity alongside traditional transport links. The share of the region's residents who work outside their local authority has generally fallen since 2016. This has been especially noticeable among those from North Somerset and South Gloucestershire, though these districts still have the highest proportion of residents working in other local authorities.

Overall, the region's commuting patterns underscore the need for coordinated, cross-boundary transport planning and investment in both physical and digital infrastructure to support productivity, mobility and inclusive access to employment across the wider city-region.

Summary

The West of England's labour market performs strongly overall, with employment, earnings and skills levels all exceeding national averages. However, this masks widening internal disparities. Employment remains robust, particularly in South Gloucestershire, and while unemployment has fallen over the decade, it remains higher in parts of Bristol. Economic inactivity is lower than the national average but increasingly driven by long-term sickness, especially in Bristol.

The region benefits from a persistent wage premium of around 5% compared with the UK (excluding London). This is supported by high-value

sectors, which exhibit even higher wage premiums – these include advanced manufacturing (12%), digital technologies (10%), creative industries (7%) and environmental goods and services (9%). Yet real wage growth, which takes the cost of living into account, has remained relatively flat since 2015, underscoring the need for productivity-led growth. Wage advantages vary locally, with Bristol and South Gloucestershire showing the strongest, broad-based sectoral performance.

The labour market has been resilient to shocks, but COVID-19 and Brexit have left lasting effects in the region, including reduced employment levels relative to expected trends and a widening performance gap between large firms and SMEs, where turnover growth has weakened sharply. Workforce structure is dominated by high-skill employment, but access to good-quality work varies: South Gloucestershire consistently performs well, while North Somerset lags.

Youth participation presents a notable risk, particularly in Bristol where the youth NEET rate has risen sharply to nearly 6%, now above the national average.

Commuting patterns show a highly integrated regional labour market centred on Bristol, with hybrid working now embedded. This elevates the importance of good digital connectivity and transport infrastructure.

Overall, the region has a competitive but increasingly uneven labour market. Addressing internal divergence, boosting productivity, supporting SMEs, improving job quality, and tackling inactivity and youth disengagement will be central to securing inclusive and sustainable growth in the region.

Skills and education

Matt Dickson, Judith Delaney

Skills and education

The West of England has one of the most highly-skilled workforces in England, but the benefits of this strength are unevenly realised across the region.

Introduction

The West of England is home to over one million residents and contributes around £54 billion a year to the UK economy. Its strong productivity is closely tied to the skills and qualifications of its workforce. This chapter provides the first comprehensive assessment of the region's human capital (a measure of skills and education), comparing it with England overall and exploring differences within the four local authority areas.

The analysis centres on four questions: How does educational attainment in the region compare with the national picture? How do the four local authorities differ from each other? How effectively does the region match qualified workers, especially graduates, to suitable jobs? And to what extent do workers commute within the region for employment and how do these patterns differ by education level? Addressing these questions offers practical insights for policymakers and business leaders seeking to strengthen productivity and unlock the full potential of the West of England's workforce.

The analysis in this chapter draws on the Annual Population Survey (APS) 2015-24, accessed via the UK Data Service Secure Lab. The APS is the UK's largest household survey, providing detailed information on education, employment and a range of demographic characteristics for approximately 280,000 individuals each year. It is designed to produce reliable estimates at the local authority level.

Educational attainment – a competitive advantage

The West of England has an educational advantage compared with England as a whole, and this advantage has been growing over the 10 years from 2015 to 2024. The region has markedly more residents whose highest educational qualification is an undergraduate degree or higher – 46.9% compared with the 37.6% in the rest of England. Almost one in two residents in the West of England has at least a first degree, and the region has a higher proportion than England of those with only a first degree (25.7% versus 19.0%), those with a master's degree (8.5% versus 6.8%), and those with a PhD (2.3% versus 1.4%), as shown in Table 7. In all cases, these gaps have been consistent or growing over the last decade. The region has lower proportions than the rest of England in every category of education below degree level and much lower levels of those in the basic/no qualifications category.

Table 7: Distribution of educational qualifications by region

Highest level of qualification	West of England	Rest of England	Difference
Degree or higher	46.9%	37.6%	+9.3pp
Higher education sub degree level	6.4%	6.6%	-0.2pp
A-levels and equivalent	20.6%	21.7%	-1.1pp
GCSEs (5+)	17.4%	20.3%	-2.9pp
Lower/no qualifications	8.7%	13.9%	-5.2pp

Source: Authors' calculation based on Annual Population Survey, 2015-24.

The West of England's high concentration of graduates, particularly at master's- and PhD-level, underpins a skilled, adaptable workforce capable of supporting high-value, high-skill jobs. These advanced qualifications also fuel R&D, boosting the region's capacity for innovation and making it an attractive location for innovative and knowledge-intensive firms. A key policy question is whether this comparative advantage in highly-skilled labour is fully recognised by national and international companies, and

whether more can be done to promote the region as a hub for high-skill investment.

STEM strength

Among graduates in the West of England, 47.3% have their highest degree in a STEM field (science, technology, engineering, maths), 4 percentage points (pp) higher than the rest of England (see Table 8). This is offset by a 2.8pp lower share of graduates from business or law related degrees, with the West of England being comparable with the rest of England in terms of graduate share outside of STEM and business/law degrees. Again, these differences have been largely stable for the last decade, reflecting a consistent advantage for the region in the availability of highly-skilled workers in STEM fields.

Table 8: Distribution of graduate field of study by England and West of England region

Subject area	West of England	Rest of England	Difference
STEM	47.3%	43.3%	+4.0pp
Business, law	15.7%	18.5%	-2.8pp
Other	37.1%	38.2%	-1.1pp

Source: Authors' calculation based on Annual Population Survey, 2015-24.

Professional performance

The educational advantage that the West of England has relative to the rest of England translates into an occupational structure that is heavily weighted towards professional and semi-professional occupations and away from routine jobs. In 2024, the region had a professional occupation share almost 8pp higher than the rest of England, with lower proportions in semi-professional and routine occupations (see Table 9).

What's more, over the last decade, there has been strong growth in professional occupations in the region. While the gap with the rest of England narrowed during the period of the pandemic, since 2022 the professional job share has accelerated in the West of England while plateauing in the rest of the country, such that by 2024 the gap was 8pp. Within the region, as with the rest of England, the proportion of semi-professional occupations has been falling across the same period, as has the proportion of routine roles. But in each case the falls have been more pronounced in the West of England, particularly in the post-pandemic period.

Table 9: Distribution of occupation type in England and West of England region

Occupation type	West of England	Rest of England	Difference
Professional	61.0%	53.3%	7.7pp
Semi-professional	23.2%	26.9%	-3.7pp
Routine	15.8%	19.8%	-4.0pp

Source: Authors' calculation based on Annual Population Survey, 2015-24.

The West of England's high concentration of STEM graduates is a clear economic asset, providing a deep pool of skilled labour for advanced manufacturing, digital and research-intensive industries. However, the evidence raises questions about whether this strength is being fully leveraged to maximise regional productivity and innovation.

The accelerated growth in professional and high-skill occupations in the region since the pandemic indicates strong demand for highly-qualified workers and a regionally dynamic economy. Sustaining this momentum will require policies that actively connect the region's STEM skills base to the expansion and attraction of high-value firms, ensuring that skills supply translates into high-quality job creation across the region.

A tale of two tiers

While the West of England has a distinct educational advantage compared with the rest of England, this is unevenly distributed within the region. There are two distinct groups – Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset which drive the region’s educational advantage, and South Gloucestershire and North Somerset, which have education profiles closer to those of the rest of England than to their West of England neighbours.

In Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset, approximately one in every two people is a graduate, whereas in North Somerset, the figure is one in every three, and South Gloucestershire sits somewhere in between (see Table 10). The proportion of residents with A-levels as their highest qualification is also particularly different for Bristol, where the figure is about half that for the other areas (which are all in line with the rest of England).

Table 10: Distribution of educational qualifications within the West of England

Highest level of qualification	Bristol	Bath and North East Somerset	South Gloucestershire	North Somerset
Degree or higher	53.4%	48.6%	42.1%	34.2%
Higher education sub degree level	4.3%	6.0%	6.6%	8.7%
A-levels and equivalent	11.3%	22.9%	24.5%	23.9%
GCSEs (5+)	12.5%	15.5%	16.9%	24.6%
Lower/no qualifications	9.1%	7.0%	9.9%	8.5%

Source: Authors' calculation based on Annual Population Survey, 2015-24.

While North Somerset has by far the lowest proportion of graduates, it has the highest proportion for whom GCSEs are the highest qualification by some margin – approximately one in four. These differences have been

largely persistent over the last decade, with Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset following a distinct pattern that differs from South Gloucestershire and North Somerset, particularly in terms of graduate share and proportion with GCSEs as the highest qualification.

The pronounced imbalances in education and skills across the West of England point to the need for place-based policy responses that strengthen local skills pipelines. North Somerset stands out in particular; with a substantially lower share of graduates and a much higher proportion of residents whose highest qualification is GCSEs.

Barriers to commutable access to the region's universities are likely to be a contributory factor in the lower share of graduates among residents in North Somerset, and this is likely to continue if not addressed. In the latest UCAS data from 2025⁴, 31% of 18-year-olds accepted for undergraduate study reported that they plan to live at home during their university education. As such, the lack of access to higher education institutions for North Somerset residents represents a major impediment to the area's educational attainment.

South Gloucestershire has some issues in terms of the supply of higher education opportunities, though not as acute as North Somerset. South Gloucestershire is home to the main campus of University of the West of England, but other than this the higher education provision within its borders is limited to South Gloucestershire and Stroud (SGS) College, which is a college of further education that has university centre status. Residents of South Gloucestershire can potentially commute to other universities in the region – University of Bristol, University of Bath and Bath Spa University – but it is notable that the area's proportion of graduates is lower than is the case for Bath and North East Somerset and Bristol, and they have the highest proportion of residents who gain A-levels but do not go on to higher education. This suggests a leakage in the skills pipeline despite good access to post-16 education and commutable proximity to universities.

Targeted interventions to improve access to higher education provision, particularly in North Somerset and South Gloucestershire, would help to address these structural imbalances and support a more even distribution of skills across the West of England.

⁴ <https://www.ucas.com/corporate/news-and-key-documents/news/more-school-leavers-living-at-home-for-university-and-college-study>

Job matching success

The West of England performs strongly on job matching – matching workers to jobs that are commensurate with their levels of skills – with workers less likely to be underemployed than elsewhere in England (28.6% versus 35.3%). This pattern is consistent over the past decade but widened after the pandemic. This advantage is driven overwhelmingly by Bristol, where only 20.4% of workers are underemployed, compared with much higher rates in South Gloucestershire (30.5%) and especially North Somerset (36.9%).

Graduate matching tells a similar story: the region has lower graduate underemployment (17.4%) than England (21.2%), but once again this strength is anchored in Bristol, where only 13.4% of graduates are in non-graduate roles. Bath and North East Somerset, South Gloucestershire and North Somerset all hover around the national average, and the apparent advantage in Bath and North East Somerset and North Somerset disappears once worker characteristics – such as age, background and qualification mix – are accounted for.

After adjusting for demographics, only Bristol retains a significant job matching premium: its graduates are 3.3pp less likely to be underemployed than similar graduates elsewhere in England, especially in business, law and other non-STEM fields. South Gloucestershire shows the opposite pattern – graduates there are more likely to be underemployed, particularly in STEM and non-business/law fields – highlighting a misalignment between supply and local job opportunities.

Taken together, the evidence shows a region with strong overall job matching but stark internal differences. Bristol operates as the standout labour market, efficiently absorbing both its own graduates and those from neighbouring areas, while South Gloucestershire and North Somerset struggle to convert local qualifications into high quality employment. This underscores the importance of a focus on creating growth opportunities for higher-value businesses across the region and the need for place-sensitive skills and employer engagement strategies to close these gaps.

Home to work

Commuting patterns in the West of England reveal Bristol's dominant role as the region's employment hub. While 63% of Bristol residents work within the city, the picture is very different for its neighbours: only 34% of South Gloucestershire residents and 49% of North Somerset residents work locally, with large shares commuting into Bristol instead. For South Gloucestershire, this is so pronounced that more residents work in Bristol than in their own authority – a clear illustration of Bristol's gravitational pull.

This pattern intensifies among graduates. Bristol retains 72.6% of its graduate residents in local employment, compared with just 34.4% for South Gloucestershire and 45.7% for North Somerset, underscoring how high-skilled workers cluster around the city. Meanwhile, significant proportions of graduates from Bath and North East Somerset (12.4%) and South Gloucestershire (38.2%) commute daily into Bristol, reinforcing its position as the centre of high-skill employment in the region. This also highlights the region's highly-integrated labour market.

Even among workers with GCSEs as their highest qualification, Bristol remains the key destination. Roughly one-third of lower-qualified residents of South Gloucestershire commute into Bristol, again mirroring broader labour market dynamics. This shows that Bristol's pull extends beyond high-value sectors, shaping opportunities for workers at all education levels.

Together, these patterns highlight a deeply integrated regional labour market that relies heavily on Bristol as an engine of employment. This has major implications for transport, housing and local economic development and emphasises the importance of ensuring that residents can access high-quality work from wherever they live within the region.

Summary

The West of England has a consistently strong skills base, with a significantly higher share of residents educated to degree level than the national average. This provides a solid foundation for high-value employment and supports the region's productivity. The region also has an above average concentration of STEM graduates, contributing to the labour supply for advanced manufacturing, digital and research-intensive sectors.

However, this strength is unevenly distributed. Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset drive the region's high qualification profile, while South Gloucestershire and North Somerset residents have lower graduate shares and a greater proportion of residents with mid-level or GCSE-level qualifications. These differences shape local labour market outcomes, including the types of occupations available and the extent to which workers are matched to roles aligned with their skills.

Job matching across the region is stronger than the national average, but this advantage is largely concentrated in Bristol, which absorbs a substantial proportion of high-skilled workers, including graduates from neighbouring authorities. In contrast, South Gloucestershire and North Somerset experience higher rates of underemployment and weaker alignment between qualifications and job roles.

Commuting patterns reflect these dynamics. Bristol functions as the region's primary employment hub for both graduates and lower qualified workers, reinforcing its central role in the skills ecosystem. This reliance on a single core labour market underscores the importance of transport connectivity.

Overall, the region benefits from a strong skills base, but internal disparities limit the extent to which this advantage is shared. Strengthening local education pathways, improving access to higher level skills, and enhancing access to job opportunities for residents who live outside Bristol through accessible transport solutions will be essential to support more balanced and inclusive growth.

Migration

Aida Garcia Lazaro, Daniel Jin

Migration

International migration to the West of England is modest in scale but rapidly diversifying, driven largely by young people and international students. Net internal migration has reduced significantly within the region, largely led by individuals moving out of Bristol and Bath's urban economies, suggesting a reconfiguration of where people live within the region.

Introduction

This chapter provides analysis of both national and international migration and mobility in the West of England, drawing on publicly available data to examine how the scale, composition and dynamics of population movement have evolved across the region. It explores patterns of international, domestic and internal mobility; trends in the non-UK-born and non-UK-nationality populations; and the specific roles played by students, workers and families in shaping local demographic change.

By comparing the West of England with other combined authorities and disaggregating flows by age, gender, origin and household type, the chapter highlights the West of England's emerging but still comparatively modest migration profile, as well as the differing pressures and opportunities faced by each local authority within the region.

Mobility in the region

Internal migration across the West of England has generally been characterised by stronger inflows than outflows since 2012, positioning the

region as a net receiver of population. However, this net inflow has weakened, with a marked contraction around the COVID-19 pandemic, which is consistent with a broader reduction in mobility throughout the UK.

From 2021 onwards, Bristol and, to a lesser extent Bath and North East Somerset, became net exporters of people, contributing to the slowdown in the regional aggregate. In contrast, South Gloucestershire and North Somerset have displayed comparatively steadier and more persistent positive net inflows across the period. This pattern suggests that the overall reduction of the regional net balance has been driven primarily by shifts in the largest and most dynamic urban centres rather than by a uniform decline across all authorities.

The relative stability of North Somerset and South Gloucestershire likely reflects differences in local economic structure and housing market affordability. These steadier positive net inflows may be associated with residential preferences and housing developments rather than rapid employment expansion alone. The area may be attracting households seeking lower-density areas or more affordable locations, while maintaining access to the urban labour markets. This dynamic has likely intensified since the pandemic, as remote and hybrid working arrangements have increased the feasibility of commuting over longer distances on a less frequent basis.

Looking at mobility within the West of England, Bristol is the most dynamic region, facilitating the largest amount of inter-authority moves. Looking at the trends in these data (2012-24), this pattern of net outflow from Bristol to other West of England local authorities has only been reinforced. Notably, this dynamic was well established and being strengthened before 2020, suggesting that the observed redistribution was not solely a pandemic-related effect, but part of a broader structural shift in residential location.

The scale of change is particularly marked for South Gloucestershire, which now receives roughly three times more net inflows from Bristol than it did in 2012 (3,141 up from 1,215). North Somerset has also seen a substantial rise, with net inflows from Bristol approximately doubling relative to 2012 levels (2,043 up from 1,011). By contrast, exchanges between Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset have increased more moderately (255 up from 188).

Figure 14: Net internal migration in the West of England by local authorities, 2012 - 2024

Source: Internal migration in England and Wales; moves by local authorities, years ending June 2012 to June 2024.

Migration trends

Migration into the West of England has risen steadily since 2010, with the non-UK-born population increasing from around 9% in 2010 to roughly 12% by 2023. While growth has been somewhat faster than in comparable combined authorities, the region still hosts a smaller migrant population overall (see Figure 15). Much of this rise occurred from the mid-2010s onwards, reflecting the region's shift from a low-migration area towards a more diverse and internationally connected one.

Figure 15a: Migrant population share by country of birth in selected combined authorities, 2010-23

Source: NOMIS, ONS annual population estimates, 2010-23.

Notes: Non-UK-born population includes EU-born and non-EU-born.

Across the entire period, the West of England records lower shares of non-UK-born population than Cambridge and Peterborough, Greater Manchester and West Midlands. This relative position is stable over time and reflects the region’s smaller metropolitan scale and more recent development as a migration destination. Despite these lower levels, the share of non-UK-born population increases steadily over the decade.

Although starting from a lower base, the West of England shows comparative expansion in migration across the period (2010-23), when growth is indexed to 2010, allowing comparison of proportional change independently of initial size across combined authorities (see Figure 16). This shows a 30% increase relative to the baseline year (2010=100) – a notable acceleration in the non-UK-born population. In proportional terms, its trajectory broadly keeps pace with that observed in larger combined authorities.

Figure 15b: Migrant population share by country of birth in selected combined authorities, 2010-23

Source: NOMIS, ONS annual population estimates, 2010-2023.

Notes: The population share of non-EU-born is disaggregated by Asian-born, African-born and North, Central and South American-born as shown in the second row.

The growth of the non-EU born population is particularly accentuated in the West of England, driven by an 100% increase in the Asian-born population in the first half of the decade, relative to their 2010 baseline, followed by a partial reversal in later years. By contrast, Africa-born populations have increased more steadily toward the end of the period, and the North, Central and South American born population show a positive trend since the COVID-19 pandemic, pointing to gradual diversification (even where initial shares remain comparatively small). This has led to the region’s migrant profile becoming more varied over time.

Notably, the West of England appears to be far more sensitive to policy shocks than other combined authorities, including the EU referendum and the pandemic, which influenced both EU-related mobility and the scale of temporary migration. The region saw a pre-Brexit surge (2016-19) as EU

residents secured their status, as well as a post-Brexit contraction (2020-22) driven by legal changes and naturalisation. The pandemic temporarily suppressed both international and internal migration, with noticeable dips in student migration, EU and non-EU inflows and domestic population movement.

Figure 16a: Migrant population share by country of birth in selected combined authorities, 2010-23

Source: NOMIS, ONS annual population estimates, 2010-23.

Notes: Highlighted the West of England; index (2010 = 100). Non-UK-born population growth includes EU-born and non-EU-born.

Overall, the data point to a region undergoing gradual, uneven diversification, rather than large-scale structural demographic change. Migration is playing a growing role in shaping the population, but from a modest starting point and with patterns that differ markedly from larger metropolitan areas.

Figure 16b: Migrant population share by country of birth in selected combined authorities, 2010-23

Source: NOMIS, ONS annual population estimates, 2010-23.

Notes: The population growth of non-EU-born is disaggregated by Asian-born, African-born and North, Central and South American-born in the second row.

In addition, comparing data of both the country-of-birth and nationality data adds a further level of detail. While the non-UK-born population has grown, the non-UK-nationality population has remained relatively stable and even fell between 2019 and 2021. This reflects naturalisation, settlement over time and the expanding presence of international students, who contribute to population change but typically do not acquire UK nationality. These dynamics underscore the need to interpret migration through multiple indicators, not just nationality or birthplace alone, and to recognise the distinctive blend of long-term settlement and high-turnover student migration shaping the West of England today.

Migration and higher education

Higher education is a major engine of international migration into the West of England. The region's universities have seen the number of international students climb steadily over the past decade, rising by around 39% between 2015 and 2024 to reach approximately 25,000 students. The West of England shows a clear upward trajectory between 2015 and 2024, with international students accounting for an increasing share of total students, 14% in 2015 and 18% by 2024. In contrast, although the West Midlands and Great Manchester have a larger proportion of international students in 2015 (22% and 18% respectively), they show a steadier trajectory and less change (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Number of international students across combined authorities in England

Source: Higher Education Student Data, HESA.

This surge in student migration has reshaped the region's demographic profile, particularly in Bristol and Bath, where international arrivals are heavily concentrated among 16-34-year-olds. It helps explain why the non-UK-born population has grown more sharply than the non-UK-nationality population: student migrants boost diversity and headcount, but their presence is often temporary, with limited routes to citizenship during study.

The influence of higher education is also reflected in household patterns. University-centred areas show much higher shares of international migrants arriving neither in family units nor living in communal establishments, while areas with fewer students, such as North Somerset, see migrants arriving primarily as couple families. This underscores how student-driven migration brings distinctive needs and pressures, from housing churn to transport demand and integration support.

Overall, international students are a central driver of migration trends in the West of England, shaping age structure, nationality patterns, household types, and the pace of population turnover in key localities.

Household types and migration pathways

International migrants arriving in the West of England show distinct household patterns that vary sharply between local authorities, based on UK Census 2021 data. In Bristol and Bath and North East Somerset, arrivals are spread across multiple household types, with large shares coming as couple families (around a third), significant numbers arriving not in a family, and unusually high proportions living in communal establishments. These patterns are a clear sign of the strong influence of international students in these university-centred areas.

In contrast, North Somerset presents a highly family-oriented migration profile: over two-thirds of arrivals come as part of a couple family, with very small share living in communal establishments. This suggests migration here is driven more by long-term settlement and employment than temporary or education-linked flows.

South Gloucestershire sits in the middle, with just over half of arrivals in couple families but with notable proportions arriving as individuals or in communal settings. This mixed pattern reflects its combination of residential areas, commuter links and STEM-related employment opportunities.

Together, these variations show that migration into the region is not one-size-fits-all. Different household types reflect different migration drivers from students and young professionals to families seeking

longer-term settlement, reinforcing the need for place-sensitive planning around housing, services and community integration.

Summary

The West of England is experiencing steady but modest international migration. Overall, the non-UK-born population has grown faster here than in comparable combined authorities, but from a much smaller base. This indicates that the region is diversifying gradually rather than undergoing a major demographic transformation. Domestic mobility is likely to have a more significant effect on authorities' population. While the region as a whole has remained broadly attractive, the internal balance has shifted. Bristol and, to a lesser extent, Bath and North East Somerset have moved from being net receivers, or broadly balanced, to becoming net exporters of population, while South Gloucestershire and North Somerset have absorbed an increasing share of residential relocation.

Migration into the region is highly age-selective, dominated by 16-34-year-olds, and varies sharply by place and household type. Bristol and Bath see diverse inflows, including large numbers of students and young professionals, while North Somerset attracts mainly family-based migrants and longer-term settlers. South Gloucestershire has a mixed profile, reflecting its STEM-oriented labour market. Crucially, trends are more volatile than in long-established migration hubs, with flows sensitive to policy and economic shocks, such as Brexit and the pandemic. Together, these patterns show a region becoming more internationally connected but in place-specific ways that will require tailored planning for housing and services.

Infrastructure

Joe Chrisp, Yadira Gómez-Hernández, Finlay Perry

Infrastructure

Infrastructure in the West of England is struggling to keep pace with the region's growth, with high housing costs, congested and unreliable transport and patchy digital provision, creating real barriers to productivity and inclusion. Despite major investment programmes and pockets of strong performance, the region faces a critical need for coordinated, long-term action to ensure that homes, connectivity and mobility support, rather than constrain, its economic potential.

Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive assessment of the West of England's housing, transport and digital infrastructure, examining how each system underpins economic performance, spatial development and social inclusion across the region. It brings together quantitative analysis, national and regional evidence to evaluate current provision, identify structural constraints, and highlight where infrastructure is failing to keep pace with growth. By considering these domains together, the report takes a whole-systems view of how homes, mobility and connectivity interact and what this means for the region's future prosperity.

Digital

Digital connectivity is now fundamental to economic performance of regional economies. High-quality broadband and mobile networks support

everything from business productivity and innovation to access to jobs, education and public services (What Works Centre for Local Economic Growth, 2015). While improved internet speed and coverage can boost firm creation, raise productivity and support high-skilled sectors, the evidence shows that benefits depend heavily on adoption, not just availability (Briglauer *et al.* 2025; Sanchis-Guarner *et al.* 2024; Briglauer & Grajek, 2004). Faster broadband tends to help service industries, skilled workers and urban areas more than rural or lower-income communities. What's more, without complementary investment, such as workforce training or organisational change, the impact on growth remains uneven.

Across the UK, national programmes – like Superfast Broadband, Project Gigabit and the Shared Rural Network – have significantly expanded fixed and mobile coverage, though not uniformly. The West of England performs relatively well on gigabit broadband and 4G availability but still has pockets of poor superfast coverage, especially in Bath and North East Somerset. There is also substantial variation in 5G rollout across the region and indoor mobile connectivity remains a particular challenge. These gaps matter: digital deprivation closely tracks wider social inequalities, reinforcing barriers for low-income households, older people, disabled residents, carers, refugees and others who already face economic exclusion.

Digital inclusion remains a major issue. More than 100,000 adults in the region are very limited or non-users of the internet, and a large share of families with children fall below the Minimum Digital Living Standard – broadly defined as having accessible internet, adequate equipment, and the skills and knowledge needed. Vulnerable groups such as older adults, low-income households, carers, refugees, and people with disabilities are disproportionately affected. Barriers include the affordability of devices and connectivity, limited awareness of social tariffs, poor design of online services, and transport challenges for accessing support, each of which contribute to persistent exclusion. While nearly 200 local organisations provide digital inclusion support, the landscape is fragmented, short-term and difficult for residents to navigate.

Looking forward, the region will benefit from treating digital infrastructure as a core component of place-based planning that is embedded into new housing, transport and low-carbon energy systems. But infrastructure alone is not enough: the region will need a coordinated, long-term approach to digital inclusion, bringing together councils, the National Health Service (NHS), universities and community organisations to align goals, share

resources and ensure that every resident can participate in an increasingly digital society.

Housing

Housing sits at the heart of the West of England’s economic story. It shapes where people live, work and build their lives, and it underpins the region’s ability to attract and retain talent. Yet affordability pressures are acute. House prices across all four local authorities exceed national and regional averages, with Bath and North East Somerset and Bristol among the most expensive places to live (see Table 11). Affordability ratios have surged over the past two decades – driven by high demand and restricted supply – and this has dampened mobility, increased hiring costs for businesses and widened inequalities between income groups and generations.

Table 11: Housing affordability in the West of England, house prices and rents

	Median house price, 2024	Mean rent, Oct 2025	House price affordability ⁵ , 2024	Rent affordability ⁶ , 2023/2024
England	£289,995	£1,416	7.71	36.3%
South West	£302,000	£1,072	8.36	31.4%
Bath and North East Somerset	£390,000	£1,770	9.70	42.7%
Bristol	£340,000	£1,824	8.72	44.6%
North Somerset	£315,000	£1,182	8.20	30.0%
South Gloucestershire	£326,250	£1,424	8.31	31.3%

Source: Source: ONS - House Price Statistics for Small Areas (HPSSA), Annual Survey of Hours and Earnings (ASHE), Price Index of Private Rents (PIPR)

⁵ The ratio of median house prices to median residence-based earnings.

⁶ The ratio of mean private rent prices to median gross monthly income of privately-renting households expressed as a percentage.

When it comes to housing, location matters – the region’s recent housing trajectory varies sharply by place. Bath and North East Somerset has long been an outlier for high prices, but since 2015, prices in Bristol, South Gloucestershire and, more recently, North Somerset have risen rapidly. This was especially the case during the pandemic and has led to a divergence from the national trend. While rents broadly mirror this pattern, Bristol’s elevated rental premium partly reflects a higher proportion of larger rental properties, rather than uniformly higher prices across all property types. As of October 2025, Bristol has the 27th highest average rents in the UK and Bath and North East Somerset 32nd highest (out of 294 local authorities listed). This places both areas above several London boroughs, and Bristol as the 5th highest local authority outside of London⁷. These high rental costs are intensifying affordability pressures for lower- and middle-income households.

Tenure patterns reveal further challenges. Despite high prices, homeownership remains comparatively strong across the West of England, especially in South Gloucestershire and North Somerset, but this masks generational divides. Younger households remain locked out of ownership, and Bristol’s housing market is characterised by particularly high rates of private renting. Meanwhile, supply continues to lag behind demand. Restrictive planning, limited land availability and the cost of construction all constrain delivery, while ambitious national targets for new homes remain unmet.

Overall, the housing landscape underscores a central policy need: improving affordability requires significant increases in supply in locations people want to live, paired with better transport and digital connectivity. Without this alignment, rising prices and rents risk undermining the region’s strong labour market, limiting inclusive growth and pushing key workers further away from job centres. The evidence points clearly to the need for coordinated, long-term planning that integrates housing with infrastructure, skills and economic development to ensure that the West of England can grow sustainably and equitably.

⁷ After St Albans, Elmbridge, Oxford and Brighton and Hove, all of which are effectively in commuting distance of London.

Transport

Transport is a defining challenge for the West of England. While the region benefits from strong intercity links, its internal connectivity is far weaker, holding back productivity, limiting access to opportunity and intensifying spatial inequalities. Congestion in Bristol and Bath rank among the worst in the UK, and public transport is often unreliable, slow and poorly integrated. This creates a system heavily dependent on cars – particularly in lower-density areas like South Gloucestershire and North Somerset – where alternatives are limited and commuting patterns dispersed. The result is a transport network that constrains growth, weakens labour market access and contributes significantly to the region’s carbon emissions.

The economic evidence is clear: improved regional transport connectivity increases employment, boosts productivity and strengthens agglomeration effects, but only when it links people to genuinely productive areas and is paired with wider investment in skills, housing and public services (Hörcher *et al.* 2020; Gibbons *et al.* 2019; Pogonyi, 2020; Rodrigues and Breach, 2021; Sanchis-Guarner *et al.* 2024).

Within the UK, enhancements to road and public transport infrastructure have raised employment and supported business activity, yet benefits can be undermined by displacement, congestion or limited local housing supply. For the West of England, these dynamics are particularly acute: the region has strong job opportunities but weak internal connectivity, meaning that people struggle to reach work even when opportunities are plentiful.

The West of England Combined Authority’s current programme, underpinned by the £1.2 billion City Region Sustainable Transport Settlement, is ambitious. It proposes new rail stations, active travel corridors, integrated ticketing and plans for a mass transit system. These investments aim to reduce congestion, expand the effective size of the labour market and create better links to new housing and economic growth zones, including major developments such as Brabazon. But delivery risks remain significant, with inflation-related funding shortfalls, back-loaded spending profiles (those concentrated at the end of a period/contract) and persistent public dissatisfaction with transport service quality. The shift to working from home adds further complexity: as workers disperse to less-accessible areas, achieving a shift away from cars becomes even harder.

Looking ahead, transport cannot operate as a standalone lever. It must be integrated with housing, digital infrastructure and climate strategies to

create genuinely accessible, low-carbon places. Mass transit has the potential to reshape the region, expanding the functional size of Bristol, unlocking development sites and improving connectivity between job centres and communities. But this will only succeed if delivered at sufficient scale and frequency to compete with the convenience of car travel. Sustainable mobility measures, from electric vehicle (EV) infrastructure to active travel networks, will also be essential but must be supported by behavioural change, affordability measures and reliable alternatives. With coordinated planning and long-term investment, transport can become an engine for inclusive growth rather than a constraint on it.

Integration

Across housing, transport and digital infrastructure, a clear message emerges. Tackling the West of England's challenges requires joined-up, place-based planning. The region's biggest constraints – high housing costs, slow and unreliable transport, uneven digital connectivity and pockets of exclusion – interact with each other. Improving one system in isolation often simply shifts pressures elsewhere. Integration is therefore essential to unlocking genuinely inclusive and sustainable growth.

Integrated planning also matters for reducing inequalities. Spatial, digital and economic exclusion overlap, meaning that investment must be coordinated across physical infrastructure, public services and community support. Without this, improvements will disproportionately benefit already well-connected, high-income households and places. A whole-system approach is particularly important in rural areas and lower-income communities, where poor transport and weak digital access reinforce limited employment opportunities.

To deliver this integration, the West of England needs long-term, aligned strategies that connect housing growth with mass transit, embed digital connectivity requirements into all new developments, and use shared data systems to target and sequence investment. The West of England Combined Authority is well-placed to play the coordinating role, linking local authorities, transport operators, developers, digital providers and anchor institutions (large, public-sector organisations such as hospitals or universities that are rooted in their communities) to ensure that infrastructure investments support one another rather than compete. By planning across systems, not sectors, the region can expand access to

opportunity, reduce inequities and create the conditions for a more productive, resilient and inclusive economy.

Summary

Infrastructure is now one of the biggest brakes on the West of England's economic potential. Despite strong underlying growth, the region's homes, transport systems and digital networks are struggling to keep pace. High housing costs are pricing out key workers and young families; congested, unreliable transport weakens productivity and limits access to opportunity; and digital connectivity, while improving, remains uneven, leaving pockets of residents and businesses without the tools they need to thrive.

Infrastructure has become a decisive factor that shapes who can participate in growth and where future prosperity is possible. The next phase of development will depend not on incremental improvements to individual networks, but on integrated, long-term planning that aligns homes, mobility and connectivity with economic development. Infrastructure must shift from being a constraint to becoming the backbone of a more inclusive, productive and resilient regional economy.

Environment

Peter Bradley, Mark Everard, Armagan Gezici, Laura DeVito, Ali Sen, Zac Mitchell, Daniel Jin, Francisco Sierra, Graham Parkhurst, Finlay Perry, Pujan Ghosh, Ian Smith

Environment

The West of England stands at a crossroads: its climate and natural environment face pressures, yet it is equipped with the ambition, assets and ingenuity to lead the UK's transition to a sustainable, resilient economy. Bold, systemic action is now essential to help the region to turn environmental risk into long-term prosperity.

Introduction

This chapter provides an assessment of the environmental and economic challenges facing the West of England, bringing together evidence on the state of the natural environment, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, land-use pressures and climate adaptation needs to inform future action.

It maps emissions across sectors; examines the condition of nature and key drivers of ecological decline; evaluates land availability and constraints for net zero and nature recovery; and synthesises the region's preparedness for climate impacts. This forms an integrated evidence base designed to support a sustainable economic transition. One that aligns prosperity with environmental limits and strengthens the resilience, equity and long-term wellbeing of the region's people and places.

Greenhouse gases

The West of England has managed to make progress on decarbonisation even as it has grown its economy. But major challenges remain, with sectors differing significantly in their emissions and in their total annual contributions.

To fully understand this footprint, and the scale of the challenge in reaching net zero, this section summarises the West of England’s scope 1 (direct) and 2 (indirect) emissions. It also presents, for the first time, a detailed breakdown of scope 1 emissions from commercial, industrial and public sectors to identify priority areas for the region’s net-zero strategy⁸.

Regional GHG emissions

The total estimated GHG emissions for the region in 2022 were 6,394 kilotonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent, KtCO₂e⁹ (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, DESNZ, 2025), as shown in Table 12. Over half (53%) of these total emissions were estimated to come from transport; most are related to road transport (32% of total emissions, or 42% if air transport GHGs are excluded¹⁰) and air transport services (21%). The second most prevalent sector is domestic household emissions (20%), followed by industrial and commercial emissions (15%), while 5% come from agriculture, 3% from the public sector and 3% from waste¹¹ (see Table 13).

If one excludes emissions associated with air transport services, the region has made substantial progress in decarbonisation in the last decade (2014-23), reducing carbon dioxide emissions by 1,825 KtCO₂e, with reduction in domestic emissions accounting for around a third of this (DESNZ, 2025). Emissions reductions progress, excluding air transport services, is comparable with other combined authorities between 2014 -2023, and only two other combined authorities had lower GHG emissions in 2023 (WECA, 2025b).

Decarbonising transport

Road transport is the West of England’s largest source of transport emissions. Meeting the region’s 2030 net-zero targets would require major behavioural change, including sharp reductions in car use and rapid EV

⁸ Based on available data and estimates for a consistent year of 2022.

⁹ Electricity emission allocated to the consuming sectors.

¹⁰ 44% in 2023, see (West of England Combined Authority, 2025).

¹¹ These percentages may be different to percentages reported in some other regional publications, primarily because they do not account for emissions from outbound flights as (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2025) do not provide these data. This study attempts to estimate them.

uptake, yet current progress falls far short. Electrification alone will not deliver the required cuts as EV uptake cannot be delivered at the required scale or speed. Further, EVs are not zero-emission across their lifecycle, and deep reductions in car use and a major modal shift would still be essential to eliminate transport emissions by 2030. Meaningful progress depends on reducing car dependence, shifting trips to buses and cycling, and better integrating transport and spatial planning.

Table 12: GHG emission profile for the West of England in KtCO₂e

Emissions allocated to sector	City of Bristol	Bath and North East Somerset	South Gloucestershire	North Somerset	West of England
Industry total	98	37	161	132	428
Commercial total	261	68	143	81	553
Public sector total	106	46	34	24	211
Domestic total	467	234	317	256	1274
Transport total	529	243	858	1825	3455
Land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) net emissions		-19	-13	-20	-49
Agriculture total	5	96	120	110	331
Waste total	100	13	39	38	190
Grand total	1570	717	1660	3757	6394
Population ('000s, mid-year estimate)	479	196	295	219	1189
Per capita emissions (tCO ₂ e)	3	4	6	17	5
Area (km ²)	235	351	536	391	1514
Emissions per km ² (kt CO ₂ e)	7	2	3	10	4

Source: (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2025) and an estimate of air transport related emissions produced in this work.

The UK's share of international aviation and shipping emissions will be within scope of the country's Sixth Carbon Budget from 2033 onwards. The inclusion of aviation emissions in the region's carbon account in this analysis reflects this upcoming policy change. Outbound flights from the region in 2022 produced emissions approximately equivalent to all household emissions, highlighting aviation's major climate impact.

Table 13: GHG emission profile for transport in the West of England in KtCO₂e

Emissions allocated to transport sector	City of Bristol	Bath and North East Somerset	South Gloucestershire	North Somerset	West of England
Road transport (A roads)	133	105	143	83	464
Road transport (motorways)	73	0	437	215	726
Road transport (minor roads)	307	127	255	193	882
Diesel railways	8	8	10	7	33
Air transport services				1310	1310
Transport 'other'	8	4	12	16	40
Transport total	529	243	858	1825	3455

Source: (Department for Work and Pensions, 2024) (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2025) and an estimate of air transport related emissions produced in this work.

Nationally, aviation emissions are projected to fall by only 17% by 2040, which means it remain the UK's largest residual emitter due to slow technological progress and uncertainty over long-term solutions, such as hydrogen or electric aircraft (Climate Change Committee, 2024) (ADEPT, 2022). The Climate Change Committee therefore emphasises demand-management measures such as pricing reforms and frequent-flyer policies to keep aviation within carbon budgets. While local influence over aviation policy is limited, the region's strong aerospace sector offers significant opportunities to lead in the development of low-carbon aircraft and hydrogen infrastructure, supporting both economic growth and long-term decarbonisation.

Decarbonising domestic households

Domestic household emissions account for around 20% of the region's total direct emissions. There are two main approaches to reducing these emissions: retrofitting the existing housing stock and expanding low-carbon district heating networks (centralised systems that generate heat and hot water in one location and distribute it via insulated pipes). As most homes in the West of England are older and poorly insulated, large-scale retrofitting is essential to reaching net zero. The region has set a target to improve the

energy efficiency of 250,000 homes and 8,000 non-domestic buildings by 2030, reflecting the central role of the built environment in decarbonisation goals.

However, there is a stark divide between ambition and delivery. Since this target was set in 2022, it is estimated that the region currently has an annual delivery capacity of approximately 1,700 homes (ADEPT, 2022), which represents a 'delivery gap' of a nineteen-fold magnitude. Additionally, partial evidence suggests that overall delivery has not accelerated to target delivery levels of 32,500 retrofits per annum. Therefore, the gap between target and concrete delivery is unlikely to have narrowed since 2022 and has most likely increased to somewhere between 20-fold and a 40-fold difference in retrofitting rates to meet the 2030 target. While initiatives such as the West of England's Combined Authority Retrofit West programme and Bristol's £1 billion City Leap partnership represent important innovation, regional monitoring is limited and overall progress remains slow (WECA, 2024) (Bristol City Council, 2024). Without a rapid expansion of retrofit capacity and coordinated governance, the region will fall short of its 2030 goals.

Decarbonising the commercial, industrial and public sectors

The commercial and industrial (C&I) and public sectors are clear priorities for reduction of Scope 1 emissions in the West of England, as revealed by sector-based employment models and company level data (see Tables 14 and 15). When emissions from flights are included, air transport services form the region's largest source (22%), followed by gas-fired electricity generation (12%) and the manufacture of concrete, cement and plaster products (11%). Waste collection and treatment (10%), along with agriculture, freight/logistics and human health services, also contribute substantially. Together, the top 15 sectors account for over 80% of all direct C&I emissions, with 60% concentrated in the top five. This highlights the strategic value of focusing decarbonisation efforts on a small number of high-impact activities.

Crucially, the sectors responsible for most emissions are not the region's major employers. Nine of the top 15 sectors by employment are low GHG emitters, while the five highest-emitting sectors make up only 1.8% of total

employment. This suggests that decarbonising the C&I base can be achieved with minimal impact on total employment.

Table 14: Top 15 direct GHG contributing sectors

West of England	% Employment	% GHGs	UK	% GHGs
Air transport services (SIC 51)	0.2	22.0	Products of agriculture, hunting and related services (SIC 1)	14
Electricity production – gas (SIC 35.1/1)	0.1	12.2	Electricity production - gas (35.1/1)	13
Manufacture of articles of concrete, cement and plaster (SIC 23.6)	0.1	11.0	Air transport services (SIC 51)	9
Waste collection, treatment and disposal services; materials recovery services (SIC 38)	0.8	10.9	Waste collection, treatment and disposal services; materials recovery services (SIC 38)	6
Products of agriculture, hunting and related services (SIC 1)	0.6	6.7	Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas (SIC 6)	4
Public defence services (SIC 84.22)	1.8	6.0	Manufacture of refined petroleum products (SIC 19.2)	4
Freight transport by road and removal services (SIC 49.4)	0.7	3.3	Freight transport by road and removal services (SIC 49.4)	4
Human health services (SIC 86)	9.6	2.1	Manufacture of basic iron and steel (SIC 24.1-3)	3
Wholesale trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles (SIC 45)	2.8	1.5	Electricity production - other (SIC 35.1/5)	2
Specialised construction works (SIC 43)	2.9	1.5	Manufacture of gas; distribution of gaseous fuels through mains and steam and air conditioning supply (SIC 35.2-3)	2
Retail trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles (SIC 47)	7.1	1.2	Wholesale trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles (SIC 45)	2
Fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment, excluding weapons and ammunition (SIC 25.2-3+25.5-9)	0.6	1.1	Manufacture of cement (SIC 23.51)	2
Manufacture of gas; distribution of gaseous fuels through mains and steam and air conditioning supplies (SIC 35.2-3)	0.0	1.1	Electricity production - coal (SIC 35.1/2)	2
Food and beverage serving services (SIC 56)	6.3	1.0	Human health services (SIC 86)	2
Warehousing and support services for transportation (SIC 52)	2.6	1.0	Retail trade services, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles (SIC 47)	1
Percentage of total	36.2	82.7	Percentage of total	69

Source: Table created primarily from data from ONS (2023), the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (2025), UK Government (2025) and Bristol Airport (2022) and other relevant emissions factors data identified. Note: The percentages in this table are not

comparable with those in Table 13 as these relate to total C&I and public sector emissions (and flights in Table 13 are reallocated to airlines and their relevant C&I sector).

Table 15: Sectors with relatively low GHGs (outside of top 15) and high employment (in top 15) in the West of England

West of England Sectors	% Employment	% GHGs
Education services (SIC 85)	9.2	0.8
Public administration; compulsory social security services (SIC 84 (not 84.22))	4.1	0.8
Architectural and engineering services; technical testing and analysis services (SIC 71)	3.3	0.2
Employment services (SIC 78)	2.8	0.1
Computer programming, consultancy and related services (SIC 62)	2.7	0.1
Social work services without accommodation (SIC 88)	2.4	0.1
Services auxiliary to financial services and insurance services (SIC 66)	2.4	0.1
Services to buildings and landscape (SIC 81)	2.0	0.2
Services of head offices; management consulting services (SIC 70)	1.9	0.1
Percentage of total	31	2.5

Source: Table created with data from ONS (2023), DESNZ (2025) and UK Government (2025)

Overall, these figures indicate that targeted interventions to reduce emissions in key sectors would have limited direct impact on the majority of employment in the region, and conversely that expanding employment in the region's largest sectors does not risk exponential increases in emissions. To pursue an ambitious net-zero strategy, attention should be directed

towards the small number of high-emitting sectors, with an emphasis on targeted support and transition planning.

Natural environment

The natural environment in the West of England is a key reason why people to work and live in the region (WECA, 2025b). The region is ecologically diverse, encompassing coastal zones, prominent hills, river valleys, woodlands, grasslands, wetlands and urban green spaces, and it intersects with several National Character Areas¹².

Despite its rich mosaic of landscapes, the region is experiencing a significant decline in ecological condition. A key indicator is the poor status of designated conservation sites: 118 of 138 Sites of Specific Scientific Interest (SSSI) in the region (protected areas designated for their special wildlife, habitats, geology or landform) are classified as 'unfavourable' and 'declining', highlighting widespread habitat degradation across wetlands, grasslands and rivers (WECA, 2025b).

Woodland cover remains low at 10-12%, matching England's scarce national baseline, and the Severn Estuary – one of the UK's most important ecological systems – continues to face pressures from historical and current pollution, habitat loss and development, despite its status as a Special Area of Conservation and Ramsar site (WECA, 2025c). The region's Local Nature Recovery Strategy provides further evidence of ecological stress through its mapping of priority habitats and 'focus areas' for restoration (WECA, 2025d).

Globally, wildlife populations have declined by 73% since 1970, with freshwater species declining by 85% (WWF, 2024) (WWF, 2022). The UK is one of the most nature-depleted countries, with an average 19% fall in species abundance, 16% of species threatened with extinction, and severe declines in pollinators and farmland birds since 1970 (Burns, et al., 2023). Regional datasets mirror these patterns, showing ongoing losses among pollinators, butterflies, amphibians and reptiles due to habitat loss, fragmentation and pollution pressures, such as agricultural runoff and

¹² Natural subdivisions of England based on a combination of landscape, biodiversity, geodiversity and economic activity defined by Natural England.

wastewater discharges (Bristol Regional Environmental Records Centre, 2024) (WECA, 2024).

Intensive agriculture, urban development, land-use change, habitat fragmentation, overexploitation, invasive species and climate change are all confirmed as major pressures on ecosystems, reflecting both national assessments and local examples in the West of England (State of Nature Partnership, 2023). These include nutrient runoff affecting rivers, invasive species degrading habitats and development pressures in ecologically sensitive areas (West of England Nature Partnership, 2025). The degradation of habitats undermines critical natural services such as flood regulation, carbon storage, water purification, soil formation and pollination – all core functions underpinning regional wellbeing and economic resilience.

There is a clear and urgent need for systemic, regionwide action on nature recovery. Without restoring habitat conditions, strengthening ecological connectivity or addressing the root drivers of decline, the region risks long-term damage to its economy, public health and climate resilience.

Land use, net zero and nature recovery

Land use in the West of England is shaped by an extensive green belt, agricultural land, protected landscapes and significant flood-risk areas. Managing land across competing priorities of industrial transformation, renewable energy development, housebuilding and biodiversity conservation represents a complex challenge.

The majority of land in the region is in the Avon green belt. This includes 70.4% of the land in Bath and North East Somerset, 46.3% in South Gloucestershire and 41.5% in North Somerset. Just 5.5% of Bristol is designated, reflecting its urban character (Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Local Communities, 2024); (Bath and North East Somerset Council, 2008) (South Gloucestershire Council, 2025); (North Somerset Council, 2025). The 63,000 hectares (ha) of designated land – a special status including national parks and SSSIs – within the West of England compares with approximately 43,000 ha in Nottingham and Derby, an area with a similar population size (Campaign to Protect Rural England, n.d.).

Most non-developed land lies in Bath and North East Somerset, South Gloucestershire and North Somerset, where agriculture dominates. While these landscapes contribute to rural character and food production, they also restrict the availability of land for land-based renewable energy sources. At the same time, intensive agriculture and past development have degraded soils, rivers, habitats and biodiversity. Future demand for energy, water and land, especially from growth sectors such as artificial intelligence, could increase pressure on already constrained land and ecosystems, even with strategic planning.

Given these constraints, achieving net zero and restoring nature will be challenging and require a more integrated, region-wide land-use strategy. Priority actions include:

- Maximising distributed solar offers the most immediate route to expand renewable capacity without additional need for land.
- Brownfield regeneration and industrial site reuse offer opportunities for renewable energy development on previously developed land, though site selection must carefully account for flood vulnerability. While areas such as Avonmouth and Severnside host existing industrial capacity, their documented flood risks raise questions about long-term viability for critical net-zero infrastructure. Strategic planning could prioritise less-constrained brownfield sites where such production/manufacturing does not have adverse environmental or human health implications for localised populations.
- Integration of nature recovery priorities into current land use and new development will be essential. The Local Nature Recovery Strategy maps focus areas where habitat creation and renewable development can also be aligned, helping to reduce ecological conflict (WECA, 2025d).

Nature recovery through the Local Nature Recovery Strategy, habitat connectivity and targeted restoration will be essential, not only for biodiversity, but also for climate resilience, flood management and long-term regional prosperity. Coordination across local authorities, combined with clear spatial priorities, will be fundamental to balancing land for net zero, nature recovery, food security and economic development.

Climate adaptation

The West of England faces growing climate risks that are already affecting people, infrastructure and the regional economy. Flooding remains the most significant threat, with the River Avon triggering 89 flood alerts over the past five years (Urban Water, 2025) (Thomson Environmental Consultants, 2024). Coastal and estuarine areas, such as Avonmouth and Severnside, face rising sea levels and tidal hazards, putting 17km of coastline and key industrial assets at risk (ASEA Project, 2021). Projections for North Somerset show potential sea level rise of 1-2 metres over the next century, amplifying these vulnerabilities (North Somerset Council, 2025).

Alongside flooding, the region is experiencing more frequent extreme heat events, with 30% of adults reporting impacts last year (WECA, 2024). Even in a low-emissions scenario, summer temperatures in Bristol are expected to be 1.3°C higher in 2050 than they were in 2000, while rainfall patterns shift toward drier summers and wetter winters (MET Office, 2024). Drought and water scarcity present a further emerging challenge, with the wider West Country forecast to face a 202 million-litre daily deficit by 2050 – equivalent to the water needs of 1.87 million people (West Country Water and Environment, 2025)¹³.

Local authorities recognise these threats but vary in their levels of preparedness and across the region, progress is hindered by significant funding gaps, constrained capacity, and governance that relies heavily on project-by-project collaboration rather than long-term system-wide planning. Climate impacts also fall unequally, disproportionately affecting more deprived communities, particularly in areas that are vulnerable to both heat and flooding.

Summary

The West of England is at a pivotal moment: environmental pressures are being felt, yet the region has the assets, expertise and ambition to become a leader in sustainable growth. The evidence shows a region facing decarbonisation challenges, degraded natural systems, constrained land

¹³ In relation to predicting future climate change impacts, also see: <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/approach/collaboration/ukcp/summaries/index>

availability and mounting climate risks – all of which directly shape economic resilience, wellbeing and long-term prosperity.

Greenhouse gas emissions remain heavily concentrated in a small number of sectors. Transport alone accounts for over half of all direct emissions, driven by road transport and flight-related emissions from air travel. Household emissions make up a fifth of the total, reflecting an older, energy-inefficient housing stock, while evidence indicates that commercial and industrial emissions are significantly under-reported in official datasets. Our new modelling shows that a small cluster of high-emitting sectors account for over 80% of direct C&I emissions. Crucially, the top five sectors, which account for over 60% of C&I emissions, are not major employers, meaning that the region can make significant decarbonisation progress without directly affecting the majority of employees. It will be important to help these sectors transition to net zero.

The region's natural environment, one of its core competitive assets, is deteriorating rapidly. Most designated conservation sites are now classed as 'unfavourable' and 'declining'. Habitat loss, pollution, agricultural intensification, development pressures and climate-driven disruption are eroding biodiversity and the ecosystem services that underpin food security, water quality, flood protection and public health. Woodland cover remains low, soils are degraded, and river systems are under sustained ecological stress, mirroring national trends.

Land-use pressures are now acute. Extensive green belt designations, high-value landscapes and flood-risk areas severely limit the region's capacity to expand renewable energy, decarbonise industry or build strategically located infrastructure. Agricultural land dominates rural authorities, yet intensive practices and legacy pollution have degraded its ecological value. Meanwhile, the demand for energy, water and land, particularly from emerging technology sectors such as AI, risks compounding environmental pressures.

Climate impacts are already being felt. Flooding remains the most severe and immediate risk, affecting thousands of homes and threatening major industrial assets around the Severn and Avon. Extreme heat is rising sharply, with significant social inequalities in exposure and vulnerability. Water scarcity is emerging nationally and regionally, with projected supply deficits by 2050. The region's adaptation planning is uneven across local authorities, with funding gaps, fragmented governance and limited monitoring all slowing progress.

Despite these pressures, the region has clear opportunities to lead. Innovation in aerospace, engineering, green manufacturing, circular economy models and district energy solutions position the West of England to become a hub for low-carbon economic transformation. New approaches to land stewardship, regenerative farming, nature-based solutions and place-based energy systems offer pathways to restore nature – while supporting economic resilience and circular economy – will be critical enablers for unlocking green growth.

Inequalities

Elizabeth Green, Damian Whittard, Matt Dickson

Inequalities

Inequality across the West of England is persistent, spatially-concentrated and structurally driven – with neighbouring areas experiencing starkly different levels of harm, pressure and opportunity even within the same regional economy. High-cost stresses, such as violence-related crime, food insecurity, youth mental-health crises and child-related poverty, cluster in specific localities, generating disproportionate public-service demand and long-term economic risk.

Introduction

This chapter provides a multi-dimensional assessment of inequality across the West of England. The analysis shows that inequality is persistent and spatially concentrated, and that it is primarily intra-regional, meaning that differences within the West of England are large enough that regional averages can obscure materially different local conditions.

Rather than treating poverty, health, education and wellbeing as separate policy areas, this chapter takes an integrated view of inequality as a cumulative process: households facing income insecurity are more exposed to food insecurity, poorer physical and mental health, weaker educational outcomes, and reduced access to supportive services, with these risks clustering spatially and reinforcing one another over time.

Taken together, this chapter frames inequality not simply as an ethical or social concern, but as a core determinant of regional economic resilience. Concentrated disadvantage generates higher short-run demand for crisis

services and imposes long-run constraints on human capital formation, labour market participation and inclusive growth. The findings are intended to support prioritisation and a place-sensitive strategy by identifying where pressures are most acute, where protective factors appear strongest, and where emerging deterioration suggests a need for early intervention.

Structural inequality

This section examines the distribution of structural inequality across the West of England, focusing on the ways that disadvantage is patterned by place and reproduced through core systems that shape life chances. By taking an integrated view of inequality, we explore where disadvantage is located, how it is experienced, and how it translates into longer-term constraints on opportunity, productivity and social mobility. To do this, we seek to triangulate the lived experiences of those within West of England communities with fiscal and service datasets to capture both material conditions and the lived realities of local communities.

Absolute low income in the West of England

Across the West of England, the number of people living in absolute low income¹⁴ has risen sharply since the mid-2010s, reflecting broader national trends in stagnating real incomes and rising living costs (Department for Work and Pensions, DWP, 2024) (ONS, 2024). In 2014/15, around 40,900 children across Bath and North East Somerset, Bristol, North Somerset and South Gloucestershire were living below the absolute poverty line; by 2023/24 this had risen to over 51,000, an increase of more than 10,000 children in under a decade (DWP, 2024). Bristol accounts for the largest share of this burden throughout the period, rising from 15,378 children in 2014/15 to 20,151 in 2023/24 — an increase of nearly 5,000 children. North Somerset shows similarly substantial growth, from 15,945 to 19,682, while South Gloucestershire rose from 5,902 to 7,267. Bath and North East Somerset saw the number of children in absolute low income increase from 3,685 to 3,987 over the same period (DWP, 2024).

¹⁴ Absolute low income is where households have less than 60% of the median income in 2010/11.

Relative low income in the West of England

Alongside rising absolute poverty, the number of children living on relative low incomes¹⁵ in the West of England has also increased substantially over the past decade, indicating a widening gap between lower-income households and prevailing living standards (DWP, 2024) (ONS, 2024). In 2014-15, around 32,100 children across Bath and North East Somerset, Bristol, North Somerset and South Gloucestershire were living below the relative poverty threshold; by 2023-24 this had grown to over 44,000, an increase of nearly 12,000 children (DWP, 2024). Bristol again accounts for the largest share, rising from 16,505 to 23,396, while South Gloucestershire increased from 6,358 to 8,645 and North Somerset from 5,345 to 7,302. Even in Bath and North East Somerset, relative low income rose from 3,889 to 4,706 over the same period (DWP, 2024).

The persistence and growth of both absolute and relative low income point to deepening structural pressures across the West of England, driven by rising housing costs, inflation and weak real wage growth. While absolute poverty remains most concentrated in Bristol, the rise in relative low-income highlights growing socioeconomic stratification and the uneven distribution of regional economic gains, even in comparatively affluent areas such as Bath and North East Somerset. Together, these trends reveal an increasingly insecure and exclusionary pattern of economic recovery that is leaving a growing share of households unable to benefit from the region's prosperity.

Child poverty in the West of England

Alongside low income, looking at the distribution of child poverty across the West of England helps us further capture changes to both material hardship and inequality within the region. Across the West of England, child poverty varies sharply between local authorities, revealing significant spatial inequalities within the region (DWP, 2024) (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, OHID, 2025).

In Bristol, 19.8% of children are living in absolute low-income households, a figure that is continuing to rise and is already above the other regional local authorities and the national average. This indicates that nearly one in five

¹⁵ Relative low income is where households have less than 60% of the median income in that year

children in Bristol are growing up in households experiencing real material deprivation, highlighting a significant concentration of hardship within the city. A similar but more pronounced pattern is evident when examining relative low income, which reflects inequality in relation to prevailing living standards. Bath and North East Somerset (11.6%), South Gloucestershire (12.7%) and North Somerset (15.0%) all remain below the England average (22.1%) and show no statistically significant change, indicating relative stability. Bristol again stands out, with 23.0% of children living in relative low-income households, higher than the national average and rising still. This indicates that child poverty in Bristol reflects not only material deprivation but also deepening inequality, with lower-income families falling further behind the regional norm.

Taken together, these findings reveal a clear structural divide within the West of England. Bristol consistently experiences the highest levels of child poverty across both absolute and relative measures, reflecting the combined effects of income inequality, housing affordability pressures and concentrated urban deprivation.

Food insecurity

Food bank use within a region can be an effective indicator signalling household-level economic stress and gaps in social protection and service provision. These measures can also be reactive, identifying pressures before they materialise in welfare statistics and can help to predict future pressure on health, education and social care systems.

Food parcel distribution shows pronounced and persistent spatial inequality within the West of England. While total parcel volumes have risen across all authorities since 2018 – following national patterns relating to the pandemic and cost-of-living shocks – per-capita and per-site measures reveal much sharper divergence (see Figure 18).

Parcels per site capture the intensity of distribution activity relative to frontline infrastructure, which helps to signal strains on service delivery, often not visible in totals alone.

Figure 18: Food parcels per site, operational pressure and capacity

Source: (Trussell Trust, 2025)

Bristol and North Somerset consistently record high parcels-per-site values and often exceed the West of England combined figure. This pattern indicates sustained high throughput and suggests that pressure is concentrated into a limited number of sites, consistent with capacity constraints, service configuration choices and/or concentrated demand.

Standardising by population clarifies the geography of per-capita need. Bristol and North Somerset emerge as consistently high-intensity authorities, exceeding both the national 'mean local authority' benchmark and the West of England combined series in much of the period. In contrast, South Gloucestershire shows persistently lower parcels per 1,000 residents (see Figure 19).

Overall, the findings show that food bank use in West of England is marked by pronounced spatial inequality, with disparities widening sharply after 2020. Rising demand has been met primarily through increased throughput at existing food bank sites rather than commensurate expansion of infrastructure. This indicates that there is a growing operational strain in high-intensity areas and raises concerns about long-term sustainability and service quality.

Figure 19: Food parcels per 1,000 population, regional inequality in per-capita need

Source: (Trussell Trust, 2025)

Note: Population denominator derived from LSOA-level LAD totals

Within a national pattern – driven by the pandemic and cost-of-living shocks – substantial variation persists at the sub-regional level. While the West of England broadly mirrors national trends, differences between neighbouring local authorities suggest that food insecurity outcomes are shaped not only by macro-economic shocks, but also by local conditions, including labour market structure, housing costs, welfare access, referral and delivery practices.

Child opportunity, health and future economic capacity

Children’s health, wellbeing, and educational attainment are critical determinants of future economic participation, productivity and financial

resilience. We seek to look at a range of indicators that support us in identifying the distribution of early-life disadvantage across the region.

Educational attainment

In 2024-25, the proportion of pupils achieving Grade 5 or above in both English and mathematics GCSE ranged from 44.8% in South Gloucestershire to 48.7% in Bath and North East Somerset. North Somerset (45.5%) and Bristol (46.3%) performed between these extremes. South Gloucestershire is the only area in the region with attainment below the national average for England of 45.4%. This pattern within the region, with Bath and North East Somerset at the top and South Gloucestershire at the bottom, has persisted since 2022-23. This contracts to earlier years (from 2018-19 to 2021-22) when it was always Bristol with the lowest attainment, South Gloucestershire doing slightly better, and Bath and North East Somerset always being the highest performing area in the region.

The attainment gap between Bath and North East Somerset at the top and Bristol/South Gloucestershire at the bottom remained consistently between 7 and 10 percentage points between 2018-19 and 2023-24, but it has fallen to 3.9 percentage points (pp) in the 2024-25 data. This narrowing results from a fall in Bath and North East Somerset's attainment at Grade 5 or above and an upturn in Bristol and South Gloucestershire's results in this most recent year. It remains to be seen whether this narrowing represents more than a single year blip. For many years, the inequalities in performance have been consistent, suggesting underlying structural inequalities within the region (see Figure 20).

Among free school meal (FSM) eligible young people, attainment at Grade 5 or higher in English and maths GCSE is particularly poor in the region, with all four areas falling below the average for England (25.9%). As with the all-pupils picture, Bath and North East Somerset performs relatively better, South Gloucestershire and Bristol relatively worse. This performance at GCSE translates into poorer educational attainment later on, with the 2025 Sutton Trust Opportunity Index report revealing that two Bristol parliamentary constituencies (Bristol North West and Bristol South) are the lowest ranked in England in terms of the percentage of FSM eligible pupils who attain a degree by age 22 (Sutton Trust, 2025). Only 3.7% of FSM eligible pupils in these constituencies achieve this, compared with 15.9% of FSM eligible pupils across England overall. All areas of the West of England sit below this national average (the figure for the Bath constituency is 8.5%, for

example), which suggests that there are structural inequalities hindering opportunity for disadvantaged students wherever they reside in the region.

Figure 20: Percentage of pupils attaining Grade 5 or above in both English and mathematics GCSE

Source: Department for Education, Key Stage 4 performance tables

Early-life health and preventable conditions

Early-life health outcomes provide important indicators of both current wellbeing and future developmental trajectories. Hospital admissions for tooth decay among children aged 0-5 were substantially higher in Bristol (313.3 per 100,000) than the England average (207.2), while Bath and North East Somerset (229.3), North Somerset (193.3) and South Gloucestershire (206.1) were closer to national levels (OHID, 2025).

Respiratory health outcomes show a similar pattern. Hospital admissions for asthma among under-19s were highest in Bristol (185.7 per 100,000),

exceeding the England average (148.6), while North Somerset (162.4) showed worsening trends. Bath and North East Somerset performed substantially better than England (76.4), indicating better underlying health conditions or access to preventive care (OHID, 2025).

Risk behaviours and adolescent vulnerability

Indicators of adolescent risk behaviours provide insight into social vulnerability and future economic risk. Hospital admissions related to substance misuse among young people aged 15-24 were higher than the England average (47.4 per 100,000) across all West of England local authorities, with particularly high rates in Bristol (101.6) and North Somerset (87.3). Bath and North East Somerset (66.8) and South Gloucestershire (65.9) were also elevated relative to England (OHID, 2025).

Regional trends in teenage conception rates are persistent. Bath and North East Somerset (6.95 per 1,000) and South Gloucestershire (8.94) were lower than England (13.89), while Bristol (13.12) and North Somerset (12.81) were similar to national levels (OHID, 2025).

Mental health and emotional wellbeing

Mental health indicators reveal some of the most significant inequalities within the region. Hospital admissions for mental health conditions among under-18s varied substantially between local authorities. North Somerset reported an exceptionally high rate (376.1 per 100,000), far exceeding the England average (80.2), while Bristol also recorded elevated admissions (131.3). Bath and North East Somerset (96.0) and South Gloucestershire (81.6) were closer to national levels (OHID, 2025).

Hospital admissions resulting from self-harm among young people aged 10-24 were higher in the West of England in 2025 than the England average (266.6 per 100,000). Rates were highest in North Somerset (633.0), followed by Bristol (482.8), South Gloucestershire (476.6), and Bath and North East Somerset (434.4) (OHID, 2025).

Mental health conditions during adolescence are strongly associated with poorer educational attainment, reduced employment participation and long-term economic exclusion, making them a critical determinant of future regional economic capacity (ONS, 2024).

Implications for regional inequality and future economic resilience

Taken together, these indicators reveal substantial inequalities in child wellbeing, opportunity and health across the West of England. Bristol consistently experiences poorer outcomes across multiple domains, including educational attainment, preventable physical health conditions and adolescent risk behaviours. North Somerset emerges as a particular area of concern for mental health and self-harm admissions, indicating acute pressures affecting young people.

These disparities have important implications for the region's long-term economic resilience. Educational attainment, physical health and mental wellbeing are key determinants of future labour market participation, productivity and social mobility (ONS, 2024). Persistent inequalities in these areas risk reinforcing structural disadvantage and limiting inclusive economic growth across the region.

Crime as an indicator and driver of structural inequality

Understanding the composition of crime, rather than crime volume alone, is essential for assessing the social and economic pressures faced by local areas. Differences in the types of offences recorded can have markedly different implications for public service demand, community wellbeing and inequality, even where overall levels of crime are comparable.

The distribution of crime types is structurally similar in England and Wales, the South West and the West of England, with violence and sexual offences constituting the largest single category (see Figure 21). However, the relative share of this category is notably higher in both the South West and in the West of England than at the national level. While violence and sexual offences account for approximately 35% of recorded crime nationally, this rises to nearly 38% in both the South West region and the West of England local authorities (see Table 16).

Figure 21: Crime-type composition England and Wales, South West and West of England

Source: data.police.uk (2025).

This disproportionate weighting towards violence and sexual offences indicates that the local crime profile is weighted towards offences with higher social, health and safeguarding impacts, rather than lower-harm acquisitive or administrative offences. From an economic and service-planning perspective, this composition implies greater downstream pressure on health services, social care, victim support and the criminal justice system, even where overall crime volumes may be lower than national averages.

Anti-social behaviour (ASB) represents the second largest crime category across all geographies, accounting for approximately 16% of recorded crime nationally and around 14% in both the South West and West of England (see Figure 21). While the proportional share of ASB is slightly lower locally, it remains a substantial component of recorded crime and is strongly associated with neighbourhood-level deprivation, environmental stressors and local service capacity.

In contrast, public order offences are proportionally more prominent in the South West and West of England local authorities than nationally. Public order accounts for approximately 7% of recorded crime nationally, compared with around 10% in the regional and West of England profiles. This elevation may reflect a combination of urban density effects (particularly in

Bristol), night-time economy activity and patterns of enforcement and reporting, rather than underlying criminality alone.

From an inequality and deprivation perspective, this pattern is consistent with a crime environment shaped by social stressors, service pressures and place-based vulnerabilities, rather than by opportunistic crime alone. The findings reinforce the importance of interpreting crime statistics not solely as indicators of policing demand, but as reflections of broader socio-economic conditions that interact with health, housing, employment and community infrastructure.

This analysis demonstrates that patterns of recorded crime across the four West of England local authorities are not anomalous in structure when compared with regional and national benchmarks. However, the composition and spatial concentration of crime raise material concerns for public value, service sustainability and the equitable allocation of resources.

Importantly, the findings challenge simplistic associations between deprivation and crime that rely solely on aggregate counts or neighbourhood averages. Several authorities with lower overall crime volumes nonetheless exhibit a high proportional burden of violence and public-order offences, implying elevated service demand relative to scale. This has direct implications for horizontal equity: authorities with similar population sizes or crime counts may face markedly different cost profiles, yet current funding and performance frameworks do not consistently reflect this variation in harm or complexity.

Labour market participation and economic inclusion

A more detailed overview of the West of England labour market can be found within the Labour Market chapter of this audit. This told a story of a strong overall labour market that consistently outperforms national benchmarks. But it makes clear that outcomes vary markedly across local areas, with economic inactivity increasingly driven by long-term sickness and identifies new pressures emerging from pockets of increasing youth disengagement.

Despite the strong overall performance, we again identify structural inequalities within the region and across key groups from the ONS Annual Population Survey (APS) data from March 2025. Most notably:

- In March 2025, the West of England employment rate for men aged 16-64 (81.2%) exceeds that for women (77.3%), although both are higher than England averages (79.0% and 72.3% respectively).
- Employment rates by age also indicate strong mid-career performance. The West of England has its highest employment among those aged 35-49 (89%), followed by 25-34 (85%), with younger adults (20-24) at 73% – above England across all age bands.
- Ethnicity gaps are smaller at the regional level than in some areas nationally but remain meaningful and vary by authority. In March 2025, employment among white residents is 79.9%, compared with 74.1% for ethnic minority residents.
- Disability-related inequality is one of the most persistent challenges. The disability employment gap in the West of England has remained above 12pp between 2018 and 2025, peaking at 18pp in 2020-21 and rising again to around 16pp by 2025.

Summary

The evidence presented in this chapter demonstrates that inequality in the West of England is not peripheral to economic performance but central to it. While the region benefits from strong economic fundamentals, structural inequalities in income, opportunity, health and labour market access are creating uneven exposure to risk and weakening long-term economic resilience.

By viewing inequality as a structural economic constraint, we can see that headline strength masks substantial intra-regional disparities in income security, childhood opportunity, service access and exposure to structural harms. This work has shown that neighbouring authorities face materially different levels of structural vulnerability, service demand and long-term economic risk, despite operating within the same labour market and institutional framework.

Bristol emerges as a focal point of structural vulnerability across multiple indicators, including child poverty, intensity of food insecurity, youth disengagement, crime concentration, and reduced service access. At the same time, North Somerset exhibits particularly acute youth mental health pressures and a higher share of violence-related crime, while Bath and North East Somerset shows lower material deprivation but emerging signs of hidden financial stress and elevated anxiety. South Gloucestershire performs relatively strongly on employment and income indicators but shows rising family strain.

Conclusion

Lucy Martin, Joseph Marriott

Conclusion

The evidence is unequivocal: while the West of England remains one of the UK's most dynamic regional economies, the conditions underpinning that success are under strain. Addressing these pressures with coordinated, long-term action is essential to unleashing the region's full economic potential.

The West of England stands at a pivotal moment. This Strategic Economic Audit shows a region with exceptional economic potential – with globally competitive industries, high-quality research institutions, a highly skilled labour market and strong export performance – but one that's long-term success is increasingly shaped by deep structural constraints. The story that emerges is one of both remarkable resilience and growing pressures: an economy capable of leading the UK's next wave of sustainable growth, if it can overcome the systemic barriers that hold it back.

Productivity remains one of the region's defining strengths. The West of England, as of 2023, is the most productive combined authority in England outside London, underpinned by high-value clusters in digital technologies, advanced manufacturing, life sciences and professional services. A process-driven innovation profile, strong SME-led research activity and a dense ecosystem of internationally recognised universities provide a foundation for long-term competitiveness. Yet despite these advantages, productivity gains have not been fully translated into broad-based improvements in living standards, with flat real wages since 2015 and widening internal divergences between local economies.

This audit highlights increasing structural strain that cuts across housing, transport, digital infrastructure and labour market participation. Housing affordability – particularly in Bristol and Bath – has become one of the most significant constraints on skills attraction, business growth and inclusive access to opportunity. Transport congestion and unreliable connectivity are

reshaping mobility patterns, restricting labour market reach and dampening productivity. Digital infrastructure, while improving, remains uneven, and digital exclusion mirrors broader patterns of inequality. These pressures interact, reinforcing spatial divides and placing a brake on the region's economic potential.

Labour market performance is strong but uneven. Employment rates exceed national averages, and the region benefits from a persistent wage premium in strategic sectors, including digital, creative, advanced manufacturing and green industries. But these strengths are offset by challenges of economic inactivity driven by long-term sickness, sharply increasing rates of young people not in education, employment or training (NEET) in Bristol, and a widening gap between the growth trajectories of large firms and SMEs. Job-matching efficiency is high overall but disproportionately concentrated in Bristol, where graduate absorption and high-value employment opportunities are strongest. Surrounding authorities show weaker alignment between skills and available jobs, highlighting the need for place-differentiated labour-market interventions.

Business dynamism reflects the region's dual character: a world-class innovation ecosystem in digital, creative and high-value engineering, alongside a more fragmented landscape for non-tech SMEs struggling with finance constraints, management capacity and post-pandemic uncertainty. The evidence points to a maturing economy where firm formation is steady but scaling is uneven, and where high-growth businesses often exit through acquisition rather than remaining anchored in the region. This risks the region becoming an 'incubator economy' where early-stage value is generated locally but captured elsewhere.

Environmentally, the region faces pressures. Transport accounts for over half of emissions; domestic energy inefficiency remains widespread; and a small number of high-emitting industrial sectors account for a disproportionate share of carbon output, albeit with limited direct employment exposure. At the same time, the natural environment – a core regional asset – is deteriorating, with most designated conservation sites classed as unfavourable and declining. Climate risks, including flooding, heat stress and water scarcity, are rising and unequally distributed across communities, exposing vulnerabilities that intersect closely with deprivation and service demand.

Inequalities cut through these themes. The region's prosperity is not evenly shared: Bristol faces concentrated structural vulnerability across poverty,

food insecurity, mental health pressures and crime; North Somerset shows acute youth mental-health and self-harm risks; South Gloucestershire and Bath and North East Somerset face different but significant pressures related to family stability, housing costs and access to good-quality employment. These disparities limit labour supply, reduce resilience and constrain long-term economic capacity.

Taken together, the evidence reveals a region with immense strengths but increasing systemic friction. The West of England has the assets to be a thriving regional economy: a deep STEM talent base, globally recognised research institutions, thriving innovation clusters, strong export engines, and the entrepreneurial energy of Bristol and Bath. Realising this potential requires coordinated, long-term action across skills, infrastructure, housing, transport, digital inclusion, business support and environmental resilience. No single organisation can deliver this alone. It will require collective leadership from local authorities, businesses, universities, the voluntary, community and social enterprises (VCSE) sector and national government.

By addressing structural pressures head-on, through integrated planning, targeted investment, place-based interventions and a renewed focus on sustainable and inclusive growth, the region can convert its exceptional economic foundations into a more productive, sustainable, resilient and equitable future. The path forward is clear: if the West of England can unlock its constraints, it has the capacity not only to strengthen its own prosperity, but to stand as one of the UK's leading centres of sustainable, innovation-driven growth.

References and acknowledgements

References

- ADEPT. (2022). *Case Study: LEVELLING UP. West of England Combined Authority. Action on home energy efficiency. ADEPT*. Retrieved from <https://www.adeptnet.org.uk/sites/default/files/media/2022-12/CS%20WECA%20Retrofitting.pdf>
- ASEA Project. (2021). *FAQs - Avonmouth and Severnside Enterprise Area*. Retrieved from <https://asea-flood-ecology.co.uk/faqs/>
- Bath and North East Somerset Council. (2008). *Green Belt Supplementary Planning Document*. Retrieved from <https://www.bathnes.gov.uk/services/planning-and-building-control/planning-policy/supplementary-planning-documents>
- Beauhurst. (2023). *What Makes Bristol Such a Good Startup Ecosystem*. Retrieved from <https://www.beauhurst.com/blog/bristol-startup-ecosystem/>
- Briglauer, W., & Grajek, M. (2004). Effectiveness and efficiency of state aid for new broadband networks: Evidence from OECD member states. *Economics of Innovation and New Technologi*(33), 672-700.
- Briglauer, W., Cambini, C., Gugler, K., & Sabatino, L. (2025). Economic benefits of new broadband network coverage and service adoption: evidence from OECD member states. *Industrial and Corporate Change*.
- Bristol Airport. (2022). *Annual Monitoring Report 2022*. Retrieved 02 18, 2026, from <https://www.bristolairport.co.uk/media/gx2j4wab/annual-monitoring-report-2022-180923.pdf>
- Bristol Airport. (2024). *Annual Report 2024*. Retrieved from <https://www.bristolairport.co.uk/media/as2j1amw/brs-annual-monitoring-report-2024v2-web-version.pdf>
- Bristol City Council. (2024). *Our climate action on buildings [online]*. Retrieved from <https://www.bristol.gov.uk/council/policies-plans-and-strategies/our-action-on-climate-and-ecology/our-climate-action-on-buildings> Accessed 24.11.2025.
- Bristol Regional Environmental Records Centre. (2024). *State of Nature in the WOE*. Retrieved from https://www.brerc.org.uk/downloads/BRERC_SoN_2024.pdf

-
- British Business Bank. (2025). *Small Business Equity Tracker*. Retrieved from <https://www.british-business-bank.co.uk/sites/g/files/sovrnj166/files/2025-06/small-business-equity-tracker-report-2025.pdf>
- Burns, F., Mordue, S., al Fulajj, N., Boersch-Supan, P., Boswell, J., Boyd, R., & Bradfer-Lawrence, T. (2023). *State of Nature Report 2023. British Trust for Ornithology (BTO)*.
- Cambridge Enterprise. (2025). *Cambridge tops UK for science investment as US capital surges into tech and life sciences*. Retrieved from <https://www.enterprise.cam.ac.uk/news/cambridge-tops-uk-for-science-investment-as-us-capital-surges-into-tech-and-life-sciences/>
- Campaign to Protect Rural England. (n.d.). *Interactive map of England's Green Belt*. Retrieved from <https://www.cpre.org.uk/interactive-map-of-englands-green-belt-land/>
- Climate Change Committee. (2024). *The Seventh Carbon Budget: Technical Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/the-seventh-carbon-budget/>
- Data.police.uk. (2025). *Recorded Crime & Outcomes*. Retrieved from <https://data.police.uk/data/statistical-data/>
- Department for Business and Trade. (2024). *United Kingdom innovation survey 2023: report*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/uk-innovation-survey-2023-report/united-kingdom-innovation-survey-2023-report>
- Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. (2025). *Final UK greenhouse gas emissions statistics: 1990 to 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/final-uk-greenhouse-gas-emissions-statistics-1990-to-2023> Accessed 10.10.25.
- Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. (2025). *UK local authority and regional greenhouse gas emissions statistics, 2005 to 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/uk-local-authority-and-regional-greenhouse-gas-emissions-statistics-2005-to-2023>
- Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Local Communities. (2024). *Local authority Green Belt: England 2023-24 statistical release*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/local-authority-green-belt-statistics-for-england-2023-to-2024>
-

-
- Department for Work and Pensions. (2024). *Households Below Average Income (HBAI): 1994/95 to 2023/23*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/households-below-average-income>
- Dimos, C., & Pearce, N. (2023). *Understanding R&D, innovation and productivity in the West of England*. Retrieved from https://purehost.bath.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/301644617/IPR_report_Understanding_productivity_R_D_and_innovation_in_the_West_of_England.pdf
- Gibbons, S., Lyytikäinen, T., Overman, H. G., & Sanchis-Guarner, R. (2019). New road infrastructure: the effects on firms. *Journal of Urban Economics*(110), 35-50.
- Hörcher, D., De Borger, B., & Seifu, W. &. (2020). Public transport provision under agglomeration economies. *Regional science and urban economics*,(81).
- Institute for the Future of Work. (2025). *The Good Work Time Series*. Retrieved from <https://www.ifow.org/resources/the-good-work-time-series-2025#chapter3>
- MET Office. (2024). *Annual Average Temperature Change Projections (Local Authority) v1*. Retrieved from <https://climatedataportal.metoffice.gov.uk/datasets/TheMetOffice::annual-average-temperature-change-projections-local-authority-v1>
- North Somerset Council. (2025). *Flooding advice for residents*. Retrieved from <https://north-somerset.gov.uk/my-services/nuisances-pollution-environmental-issues/flooding-drainage>
- North Somerset Council. (2025). *Nature Emergency*. Retrieved from <https://www.natureemergency.com/councils/north-somerset-council/>
- Office for Health Improvement and Disparities. (2025). *Public Health Profile (Fingertips)*. Retrieved from <https://fingertips.phe.org.uk>
- Office for National Statistics. (2023a). *International Trade in UK Nations, Regions and Cities: 2022*. Newport.
- Office for National Statistics. (2023b). *UK Trade: December*. Newport.
- Office for National Statistics. (2023c). *UK Business Register and Employment Survey (BRES): provisional results 2022, revised results 2021*. Retrieved 03 04, 2026, from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/releases/ukbusinessregisterandemploymentsurveybresprovisionalresults2022revisedresults2021>
- ONS. (2024). *Household income and inequality, UK*. Retrieved from
-

-
- <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/personalandhouseholdfinances/incomeandwealth>
- Pogonyi, C. G. (2020). The wider economic benefits of transportation. *In Advances in Transport Policy and Planning*, 6, 129-164.
- Rodrigues, G., & Breach, A. (2021). *Centre for Cities: What levelling up really means*. Retrieved from <https://www.centreforcities.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/What-Levelling-Up-Really-Means.pdf>
- Sanchis-Guarner, R., Montalban, J., & Weinhardt, F. (2024). Home broadband and human capital formation. *Centre for Economic Performance Discussion Paper No 1979*.
- Sanchis-Guarner, R., Szumilo, N., & Vernet, A. (2024). Startup stations: The impact of rail access on entrepreneurship (self-employment) in England and Wales. *CESifo Working Paper, No. 11227*.
- ScaleUp Institute. (2023). *ScaleUp Review 2023: Greater Manchester*. Retrieved from <https://www.scaleupinstitute.org.uk/scaleup-review-2023/greater-manchester/>
- Scottish Financial News. (2026). *Archangels leverages £41m of investment in Scottish scale-ups in 2025*. Retrieved from <https://www.scottishfinancialnews.com/articles/archangels-leverages-ps41m-of-investment-in-scottish-scale-ups-in-2025>
- South Gloucestershire Council. (2025). *Climate & Nature Emergency Action Plan - Year 6 (2025/26)*.
- State of Nature Partnership. (2023). *State of Nature Report 2023*. Retrieved from https://stateofnature.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/TP25999-State-of-Nature-main-report_2023_FULL-DOC-v12.pdf
- Sutton Trust. (2025, May 15). *The Opportunity Index*. Retrieved from <https://www.suttontrust.com/our-research/the-opportunity-index/>
- Thomson Environmental Consultants. (2024). *High Flood Risk Areas and Flood Mitigation in England*. Retrieved from <https://www.thomsonec.com/news/high-flood-risk-areas-and-flood-mitigation-in-england/>
- Trussell Trust. (2025). *End-of-year statistics on emergency food parcel distribution 2017–2025*. Retrieved from <https://www.trussell.org.uk/news-and-research/latest-stats/end-of-year-stats>
- UK Finance. (2025). *Gross lending to SMEs up in 2024*. Retrieved from
-

-
- <https://www.ukfinance.org.uk/news-and-insight/press-release/gross-lending-smes-in-2024>
- UK Government. (2025). *United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland's 2035 Nationally Determined Contribution 2025*. Retrieved 12 02, 2025, from <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/679b5ee8413ef177de146c1e/uk-2035-nationally-determined-contribution.pdf>
- Urban Water. (2025). *Flood Risk Map*. Retrieved from <https://urban-water.co.uk/flood-risk-map/>
- West Country Water and Environment. (2025). *Flagship projects: Strategic Resource Options*. Retrieved from <https://www.westcountrywaterandenvironment.org/flagship-projects>
- West of England Combined Authority. (2022). *Retrofit Accelerator Full Business Case [online]*. Retrieved from <https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Retrofit-Accelerator-Full-Business-Case.pdf>
- West of England Combined Authority. (2024). *Climate and Ecological Plan*. Retrieved from <https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/what-we-do/environment/climate-ecological-strategy/>
- West of England Combined Authority. (2024). *Local Nature Recovery Strategy - Part 1: State of Nature and Opportunities for Nature Recovery*. Retrieved from https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/LNRS-Part-1_State-of-Nature-and-Opportunities_Final.pdf
- West of England Combined Authority. (2024). *Retrofit West Advice Service [online]*. Retrieved from <https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/what-we-do/environment/retrofit-west-advice-service/>
- West of England Combined Authority. (2025a). *Removing barriers to unlock broadband investment*. Retrieved from <https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/news/removing-barriers-to-unlock-broadband-investment/>
- West of England Combined Authority. (2025b) *State of the West of England. Evidence for the Growth Strategy*. Retrieved from <https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/State-of-the-West-of-England-2025.pdf>
- West of England Combined Authority. (2025c) *Open Data Portal. National Forest Inventory Woodland*. Retrieved from <https://westofenglandca.opendat>
-

asoft.com/explore/dataset/nfi-woodland/table/?disjunctive.ift_ia

/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Port-dashboard-Bristol.pdf

West of England Combined Authority. (2025d). *West of England Growth Strategy*. Retrieved from <https://www.westofengland-ca.gov.uk/about-us/our-strategy/west-of-england-growth-plan/>

What Works Centre for Local Economic Growth. (2015). *Broadband Full Review*. Retrieved from <https://whatworksgrowth.org/wp-content/uploads/15-03-10-Broadband-Full-Review.pdf>

West of England Nature Partnership. (2025). *Restoring our Rivers*. Retrieved from <https://www.wenp.org.uk/priority-programmes/restoring-our-rivers>

WWF. (2022). *Living Planet Report 2022 - Building a Nature-Positive Society*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldwildlife.org/publications/2022-living-planet-report>

Western Gateway STB. (2024). *South West Freight Strategy: Port Dashboard - Bristol*. Retrieved from Western Gateway STB: <https://westerngatewaystb.org.uk>

WWF. (2024). *Living Planet Report 2024, WWF International and Zoological Society of London*. Retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/2024-living-planet-index>,

Acknowledgements

This work is supported by Research England. Research England is one of the nine constituent councils of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). It is responsible for funding and overseeing research and knowledge exchange in higher education institutions in England.

**The
Brunel
Centre**